

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D3.3 - REPORT ON BIODIVERSITY STATUS OF SOIL MICRO-ORGANISMS AND SOIL FAUNA ACROSS THE MAJOR EUROPEAN PEDOCLIMATIC REGIONS

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D3.3. REPORT ON BIODIVERSITY STATUS OF SOIL MICRO-ORGANISMS AND SOIL FAUNA ACROSS THE MAJOR EUROPEAN PEDOCLIMATIC REGIONS

Summary

Soil biota can be grouped in 3 functional guilds according to their role in the soil ecosystem. To report on the biodiversity status across the major European pedoclimatic regions, a survey was organised and a total of 188 wheat fields of conventional and organic farming systems were sampled. From each sample, the diversity of at least one representative for each functional guild was investigated: (i) bacteria and fungi (chemical engineers); (ii) nematodes (biological regulators) and (iii) earthworms (ecosystem engineers).

High-throughput sequencing of 16S rRNA gene amplicons detected OTUs belonging to both prokaryotic domains (i.e. Bacteria and Archaea). Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Acidobacteria constituted the most abundant phyla across all regions. Prokaryotic functional gene abundance was measured by quantitative PCR (qPCR) using three genes involved in nitrogen cycling (*amoA*, *narG*, and *nirK*) and two genes involved carbon cycling (*cbbL* red-like and *GH7*). The prokaryotic community composition and the functional gene abundance clustered according to pedoclimatic conditions, whereas richness and diversity indices did not vary much. Impacts of farming system on the prokaryotic microbiome differed between pedoclimatic regions and were apparent for the Mediterranean North and Boreal pedoclimatic regions, where a high number of differentially abundant OTUs were detected between the two farming systems. Among functional genes, only *amoA* and *nirK* showed significant differences between farming systems and only in some of the pedoclimatic regions. In conclusion, pedoclimatic conditions strongly shaped the soil prokaryotic microbiome, whereas impacts of farming system (conventional vs. organic) were rather minor.

Overall, both fungal richness and diversity determined from fungal ITS amplicons were highest under the organically managed fields of the Lusitanian and Nemoral regions. Pedoclimatic region affected more than agricultural management system the soil fungal community composition. There was not a clear pattern in the abundance or distribution in the community of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi between the regions or agricultural management systems. However, both region and agricultural management system derived factors affected on the incidence of some functional fungal guilds. For instance, symbiotic fungi were more abundant in the Nemoral region. In addition, endophytes exhibiting many beneficial features were indicative for organic farming in the Atlantic North, Continental, and Lusitanian regions. In turn, results would indicate the incidence of certain pathogenic fungi under organic farming system in the Mediterranean South region.

Abundance of different microbial groups according to PLFAs showed significant differences between pedoclimatic regions, but didn't show clear patterns about differences between conventional and organic farming systems. Total microbial abundance was highest in Boreal, Lusitanian, Continental and Nemoral pedoclimatic regions, while the lowest values were found in Mediterranean North and Mediterranean South. This pattern was similar for other microbial groups such as total bacteria, gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, actinobacteria and fungi. However, for arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi the highest values were found

in Mediterranean North and Mediterranean South, while the lowest in Lusitanian pedoclimatic region.

Nematode communities were firstly separated from the soil by zonal centrifugation before molecular analysis (18S rRNA amplicon sequencing). This technical enrichment procedure made it possible to use a bigger soil sample and to reduce the sequencing of other organisms. Results revealed that almost all sampled fields contain economically important plant-parasitic nematodes. The genera *Pratylenchus* and *Paratylenchus* are the most wide-spread. Also none of the regions were completely free of a root-knot and cyst nematode infestation. Both genera contain quarantine species. Even low numbers of individuals can result in severe economic losses. More plant-parasitic genera could be detected but mostly in lower numbers and less wide-spread. Biological and functional biodiversity analyses showed that the nematode biodiversity is directed more by the region with its specific conditions concerning climate and soil characteristics, than by the farming systems. Nematode taxa showing a significant differential abundance in organic farming for all regions could not be found. However, some taxa showed a significantly increased or reduced abundance in most of the investigated regions and thus have a potential to become a general indicator for organic systems.

Earthworms were sampled once in each field by combined soil hand-sorting and AITC-extraction of three samples during the period of peak earthworm activity in topsoil, which varied locally due to severe drought conditions (from 2019 (most of the samplings) to 2021). Earthworm community metrics (total abundance and biomass and species richness) were evaluated using mixed models (GLMM). Results showed no significant effect of agricultural management (conventional vs. organic) on earthworm communities, but a great regional variation in earthworm population sizes, with the Boreal region having the highest mean total density (169 individuals m⁻²) and fresh mass (87 g m⁻²) and the southern Mediterranean regions the lowest mean abundances (less than one individual and one gram m⁻²). In total, nineteen different species were identified from all investigated regions. The species could be assigned to four ecological groups: 3 epigeic (litter dwelling) species, 2 epiendogeic species, 10 endogeic (top soil burrowing) species, 4 anecic (deep burrowing) species. Most species were found in Atlantic Central (11 species), Lusitanian (9 species) and Pannonian (9 species) regions. Our results did not show an obvious latitudinal trend, and the highest species richness was observed in the Atlantic North and central areas and in the Nemoral region. There were no differences in species richness (1-3 species in a field) between the managements. There was a positive relationship between latitude and earthworm biomass, with the highest total biomass being recorded in the Boreal region followed by Atlantic North and Nemoral regions. Regional effects were mainly explained by climate, with high long-term mean annual temperature (past 30 years) having a negative influence on the three earthworm community metrics. Minor management effects might be due to switching to more sustainable practices in conventional farming such as reduced tillage, crop diversification, application of organic fertilizers and mulching techniques.

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Introduction

Loss of soil biodiversity represents a key challenge for the European agriculture as it may adversely affect the functioning, stability, resilience and adaptability of agro-ecosystems including important ecosystem services. Therefore, the protection and enhancement of soil biodiversity should be an important objective for farmers and associated industries. Currently there is a growing awareness to safeguard biodiversity but clear measurements are still missing. The SoildiverAgro-project wants to suggest new management practices and cropping systems to enhance soil genetic and functional biodiversity for a sustainable agriculture in an ecological, economical, environmental and social point-of-view. As a first step, work package 3 of the SoildiverAgro-project aims at expanding knowledge about the current status of the biological, genetic and/or functional diversity of soil organisms in European croplands following different production systems (conventional and organic farming) across 9 European pedoclimatic regions (Task 3.4).

Although, it is still unclear whether agricultural practices can restore or maintain soil health and sustainability, it has been demonstrated before that certain agricultural management systems, like organic farming in comparison to conventional farming, more rapidly induces a higher biodiversity (Rundlöf et al., 2016). However, quantifying soil health is still dominated by chemical indicators, despite growing appreciation of the importance of soil biodiversity, owing to limited functional knowledge and lack of effective methods (Lehmann et al., 2020). Additionally, the effects of agricultural systems most probably varies between organism groups owing to their ecological traits, and assessment of soil health through complete analysis of the soil food web consisting of bacteria, fungi, nematodes, beetles, mites, earthworms, Collembola, ants, moles etc. is technically daunting (Ritz and Trudgill, 1999). Alternate to this is the use of a suite of biotic indicators that should reflect the structure and function of ecological processes and should respond to soil conditions (Neher, 2001).

Soil biota can be grouped according to their functional role (Turbé et al., 2010): (i) chemical engineers include decomposers such as bacteria and fungi, some protists, some nematodes, springtails, many mites, potworms and earthworms. They are responsible for decaying plant residues and controlling nutrient cycles; (ii) biological regulators are grazers on soil micro-organisms, or predators of soil fauna, and thus shape soil communities in space and time. This guild includes many protists and nematodes, springtails, some mites, potworms and earthworms; (iii) ecosystem engineers modify soil structure by producing soil aggregates and pore networks, which provide habitat for smaller organism and control the soil water balance and soil aeration. Potworms and earthworms belong to this guild. At least one representative of each functional group was selected to gain more knowledge on their biological, genetic and/or functional biodiversity: bacteria, archaea, fungi, nematodes and earthworms.

In each of 9 pedoclimatic regions, 10 farms of which 5 following a conventional and 5 following an organic way of farming, were selected for soil sampling. Almost exclusively wheat fields were

sampled shortly after harvest. By fixing the time point of sampling and selecting one crop (wheat or in exceptional cases another cereal) natural seasonal variation and direct effects of differential crops on biodiversity was avoided and the ability to compare results was enhanced. To further ensure that variation due to different technical approaches and operators interferes with biological variation, one laboratory was selected to process all soil samples to assess biodiversity of the selected organisms. Only for earthworms, several laboratories were selected because earthworms were characterized morphologically which requires local expertise, in contrast to the biochemical and molecular methods (PLFA, NLFA, DNA-metabarcoding and qPCR) applied for the other organisms.

This deliverable (D3.3) reports on the results of the biological, functional and/or genetic biodiversity of the investigated organisms separately in relation to the agricultural management systems (conventional vs. organic) and the 9 pedoclimatic regions (Atlantic Central (Atl_cent), Atlantic North (Atl_north), Boreal, Continental (Cont), Lusitanian (Lusit), Mediterranean North (Med_north), Mediterranean South (Med_south), Nemoral, Pannonian (Pann)). The results of each organism group will not be related with additional information concerning the different aspects within each agricultural system, the chemical and physical soil characteristics (results described in deliverable D3.2), and climatological conditions as this is the subject of another deliverable (D3.4).

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1 Prokaryotic diversity

1.1 Introduction

Prokaryotes (Bacteria and Archaea) are crucial for the stability and productivity of agroecosystems as they are involved in key processes such as the formation of soil structure, organic matter decomposition, biodegradation of organic pollutants, and cycling of essential nutrient elements such as carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur (Garbeva et al., 2004). Soil prokaryotes can furthermore be highly beneficial for plants as they can suppress soil-borne diseases and enhance plant growth. Maintaining a high *prokaryotic diversity* is, thus, essential for agriculture to ensure high-quality crop production and reducing disease, and may constitute an important indicator for evaluating soil health (Abawi and Widmer, 2000; Schloter et al., 2003).

Intensification of agricultural production may have long-term detrimental effects on soil productivity and health, including prokaryotic diversity, which may have adverse consequences for agriculture production, the environment, and public health worldwide (Kennedy and Smith, 1995; Tilman et al., 2001, 2002; Levine et al., 2011). Agricultural practices affect the physicochemical properties of soils and can thereby be key determinants of prokaryotic diversity and can be affected by soil management and treatment. Hence, prokaryotic diversity can for instance be affected by tillage, crop rotation (Lupwayi et al., 1998), pesticide application (Jacobsen and Hjelmsø, 2014), and fertilization (Zhong et al., 2010). In general, low-input farming, such as organically managed farming, is believed to exert positive effects on soil properties and the abundance and diversity of many organisms compared to conventional high-input farming employing synthetic fertilizers and pesticides (Gomiero et al., 2011). However, the direct impact of agricultural management system on prokaryotic biodiversity is often difficult to determine due to the high complexity and variability across fields, regions, and studies (Hartmann et al., 2015). Moreover, as standardization of methods across studies often is lacking and as a wide range of agricultural practices exists with various degrees of external inputs, tillage use, crop type, etc., it is often difficult to provide definitive conclusions on the impact of agricultural practices on soil prokaryotic diversity (Hole et al., 2005; Gomiero et al., 2011; Hartmann et al., 2015). Therefore, to properly assess the impact of farm management practices on prokaryotic biodiversity in agricultural soil, there is a need to standardize methods and to establish a baseline for prokaryotic biodiversity in agricultural soil, which may act as a reference for future studies.

Nutrient cycling in agroecosystems is essential to maintain plant growth and development. Carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles are mostly driven by microorganisms due to their abundance and high metabolic diversity (Burgin et al., 2011). In SoildiverAgro we those to focus on some key functional groups involved in nutrient biotransformations as outlined below.

Nitrification is the biological oxidation of ammonia (NH_3) or ammonium (NH_4^+) to oxidized N in the form of nitrite (NO_2^-) and further to nitrate (NO_3^-). Nitrifying prokaryotes (especially ammonia oxidizers) are of pivotal importance in agricultural systems for several reasons (Norton and Ouyang, 2019): 1) they compete with plants for available ammonium; 2) they increase the mobility of N through the soil matrix adversely influencing N retention in the system; 3) they contribute significantly to global warming via their direct and indirect roles (coupled nitrification-denitrification) for agricultural nitrous oxide emissions. Ammonia oxidation is considered to be the rate-limiting step of nitrification and is catalysed by the ammonia monooxygenase enzyme (AMO), which is encoded by the *amoA* gene (Li et al., 2015).

Denitrification is the reduction of nitrate (NO_3^-) to nitrous oxide or dinitrogen and is the major biological mechanism by which fixed nitrogen returns to the atmosphere from soil and water. This removal of soluble nitrogen oxide (N_2O) from the biosphere is of great importance in agriculture, where it can account for significant losses of nitrogen fertilizer from soil and contribute to climate change (Henry et al., 2004). A phylogenetically broad group of bacteria can reduce nitrate (NO_3^-) into nitrite (NO_2^-), which can then be further reduced into gaseous nitrogen compounds by denitrification or into NH_4^+ by dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonium (DNRA). Denitrification is the dominant process in soils. The ability of facultative anaerobic bacteria to respire nitrate when oxygen is limiting has been ascribed mainly to the activity of a membrane bound nitrate reductase encoded by the *narGHJ* operon (Philippot and Højberg, 1999). For nitrite reduction, two different types of nitrite reductase have been characterized: copper nitrite reductase encoded by the *nirK* gene and a cytochrome cd1-nitrite reductase encoded by the *nirS* gene (Zumft, 1997).

Carbon fixation is the assimilation of inorganic C (CO_2) to organic compounds by living organisms. Transferring carbon (C) from the atmosphere to terrestrial ecosystems is a major C sequestration measure (Midgley et al., 2010). The Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle is the major pathway for CO_2 fixation (Shively et al., 1986), and the most abundant protein on Earth, ribulose-1,5-biphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (RubisCO), catalyses the first, rate-limiting step in the Calvin cycle (Ellis, 1979). The large subunit of form I RubisCO is encoded by the *cbbL* gene in bacteria (Kusian and Bowien, 2006). RubisCO proteins can be subdivided into two major groups, the green-like and red-like groups (Watson and Tabita, 2006).

Carbon degradation (e.g. plant litter decomposition) is a major source of organic carbon in soils and a key step in nutrient recycling (Berg et al., 2001). Fungi are considered key players in organic matter decomposition in soil because of their ability to produce a wide range of extracellular enzymes, which allows them to efficiently attack the recalcitrant lignocellulose matrix that other organisms are unable to decompose (Kjøller et al., 1982; De Boer et al., 2005). Cellulose is the main structural component of higher plant cell walls, representing 35–50 % of plant dry weight, and through decomposition and transformation makes up much of soil organic matter (Lynd et al., 1999). The Glycoside hydrolase encoding *GH7* gene is widely used to evaluate cellulose degradation (Merlin et al., 2014; Hu et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2017).

In SoildiverAgro we aim to provide a status on prokaryotic diversity in agricultural wheat fields (both conventional and organic farming system) across nine pedoclimatic regions of Europe using a

combination of two complementary molecular approaches. To this end, the UCPH group employed a standardized 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing protocol to study the overall effects of agricultural management on soil prokaryotic diversity (Lassen and Brandt, 2020), whereas the UPCT group used quantitative PCR (qPCR) to measure the abundance of key functional groups of microorganisms by targeting genes (*amoA*, *narG*, *nirK*, *cbbL* red-like, and *GH7*) involved in the nutrient cycling processes listed above.

1.2 Material and Methods

1.2.1 DNA extraction and purification for 16S rRNA gene sequencing

DNA extraction was performed in accordance with the SoilDiverAgro handbook on soil biodiversity analysis (Lassen and Brandt, 2020). In brief, DNA was extracted from 0.25 g of soil using the DNeasy PowerSoil Kit (Qiagen) according to the instruction manual, except for the bead-beating step, which was conducted using the environmental sample setting on an MP Fastprep-24 instrument (MP-bio). Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen) and NanoDrop ND1000 (ThermoFisher Scientific) were employed for subsequent DNA quantification and purity assessment. Extracted DNA was stored at -20°C before 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing.

1.2.2 16s ribosomal RNA (rRNA) amplicon sequencing

PCR was used to amplify the V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene from both bacteria and archaea using the modified forward primer 515F (GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA) and the modified reverse primer 806R (GGACTACNVGGGTWTCTAAT) (Walters et al., 2016). A small-fragment library was constructed, followed by paired-end sequencing using a 250 PE Novaseq sequencer at Novogene Bioinformatics Technology Co. Ltd. (UK), resulting in at least 50.000 250-bp paired-end raw reads per sample (Q30≥ 75%).

1.2.3 Data processing and analysis

The paired-end reads obtained through the amplicon sequencing were processed using QIIME 1.9 (Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology, <http://www.qiime.org>) with default parameters unless specifically noted. High-quality reads were binned into operational taxonomic units (OTUs) at a similarity of 97%, and the most abundant read from each OTU was selected as a representative sequence. Each OTU was taxonomically classified using RDP tools (version 11, <http://rdp.cme.msu.edu/>), and a phylogenetic tree was created using FastTree (Price et al., 2009). Singletons from the OTUs were filtered, followed by removing representative sequences identified

as mitochondrial DNA or chloroplast DNA. A table of filtered OTUs was generated for further statistical analyses using R software.

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.0.3 (R core Team 2018) and R studio (version 1.3.1093). All figures were constructed using 'phyloseq' (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) and 'ggplot2' (Wickham, 2016) R packages. Alpha-diversity was determined from the raw data, whereas beta-diversity was determined from the proportional data (i.e. abundance of reads belonging to each OTU relative to the total number of reads). Observed number of unique OTUs and Shannon indices were employed to investigate alpha diversity using the *plot_diversity* function of the phyloseq package. Significant differences in mean alpha diversity between agricultural management systems (conventional vs. organic) of each region were tested using a t-test executed by the *stat_compare_means* function of the ggpubr package. Beta-diversity was investigated by using nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) in combination with permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) on Bray Curtis distance matrices using the *adonis2* function of the vegan package (Anderson, 2001, 2017). To identify taxa that were significantly associated with different agricultural management systems, we conducted a differential abundance analysis using the *ancombc* function of the ANCOMBC package (Lin and Peddada, 2020) for each region. The analysis was conducted at the OTU level using the default settings except for the following; `zero_cut=0.75`, `lib_cut=1000`, `struc_zero=TRUE`, `conserve=TRUE`.

1.2.4 DNA extraction and purification for qPCR

For soil DNA extraction, we used the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen) following manufacturer's instructions. Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen) and NanoDrop 2000c (ThermoFisher Scientific) were employed for subsequent DNA quantification and purity assessment. Purification of the obtained DNA was performed with NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select (Macherey-Nagel).

1.2.5 qPCR determination of functional gene abundance

For the construction of qPCR standards, DNA extracted from soil samples as described above, served as the template of PCR reactions. PCRs were conducted using the primer pairs listed in Table 1.1.

The expected size of the PCR products was verified by electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel in TAE buffer stained with ethidium bromide. Amplicons were purified and quantified as described in step 2.1. The purified PCR product was ligated into the pGEM®-T Easy Vector Systems kit (Promega), and the resulting ligation products were used to transform into *Escherichia coli* JM109 competent cells (Promega) following the instructions of the manufacturer. Cloning screening was performed with reamplification using the vector-specific primers pUC/M13. DNA extraction of the identified positive clones was performed using the QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit (Qiagen) and quantified with Qubit® 2.0

Fluorometer (Invitrogen). The copy numbers of each of the genes of interest were calculated from the known concentration of the extracted DNA plasmid. Ten-fold serial dilutions of plasmids were run in each qPCR assay in triplicate to generate a standard curve. The abundance of the five different genes was determined by qPCR using the Rotor-Gene Q (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) using the same primers as for cloning. Each reaction was performed in a 20 µl volume containing 10 µl of PowerUp SYBR Green Master Mix (Applied Biosystems), 0.56 µl of bovine serum albumin (Invitrogen), 400 nM of each primer, 5 µl of DNA template, and nuclease-free water. Amplification conditions are described in Table 1.2.

A final dissociation stage (melt curve analysis) was performed to detect nonspecific amplification. qPCRs products were also checked on a 2% agarose gel electrophoresis to check the specificity of the amplification.

TABLE 1.1

TARGET GENES					
Code	<i>amoA</i>	<i>nirK</i>	<i>narG</i>	<i>cbbL</i>	<i>GH7</i>
Gene definition	ammonia monooxygenase	nitrite reductase	nitrate reductase	cbbL red-like gene	cellulose degradation
Primer names	amoA1F amoA1R	nirK876F nirK1040R	narG1960m2F narG250m2R	cbbL-RedF cbbL-RedR	GH7-F GH7-R
Primer sequence (5'-3')(*)	GGGGTTTCTAC TGGTGGT CCCTCKGSAA AGCCTTCTC	ATYGGCGVC AYGGCGA GCCTCGATCAG RTRTGGTT	TAYGTSGGGCAGG ARAACTG CGTAGAAGAAGCT GGTGCTGT	AAGGAYGACG AGAACATC TCGGTCGGSGT GTAGTTGAA	GAGATCAAGCGC YTCTAYGTBCA GTCRAGCCASAG CATGTTGG
Ta (°C)	57	58	56	57	56
Amplicon size (bp)	491	165	110	-	242
Reference	Rotthauwe et al., 1997.	Henry et al., 2004.	López-Gutiérrez et al., 2004.	Selesi et al., 2005.	Tian et al., 2017.

Table 1.1. Primer pairs for each gene of interest. (*) Sequence of forward and reverse primer.

1.2.6 Statistical analysis

The effect of the pedoclimatic zone, agricultural management system, and their interaction on soil functional genes was analysed performing a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). When significant F values were obtained by zone, a further analysis with Tukey's HSD (honestly significant difference) comparison procedure was performed as a post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) to control for multiple testing. F significant values obtained in agricultural management system were further evaluated performing a pairwise t-test. Statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.0.2 (R Core Team 2020) and R

studio version 1.3.1073. All figures were made using 'ggplot2' (Wickham, 2016) R package except the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) which was built with R package 'ggfortify' (Horikoshi and Tang, 2018; Tang et al., 2016).

TABLE 1.2

STEP	# OF CYCLES	TEMPERATURE	TIME
<i>amoA</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	15 sec
Annealing		58°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	45 sec
<i>nirK</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	25 sec
Annealing		60°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec
<i>narG</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	15 sec
Annealing		60°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec
<i>cbbL</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	1 min
Annealing		57°C	2 min
Extension		72°C	2 min
<i>GH7</i>			
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95°C	30 sec
Annealing		56°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec

Table 1.2. PCR cycling conditions for the different target genes.

1.3 Results and discussion

1.3.1 Sequencing quality and taxonomic characterization

A total of 30.923.879 raw reads was obtained in this study by 16s rRNA amplicon sequencing. The raw reads were quality filtered into a total of 28.399.234 high-quality reads, ranging between 62.335 and 300.734 reads per sample. The reads were grouped into a total of 33.332 OTUs divided across two domains (Bacteria and Archaea), 60 phyla, 195 classes, 360 orders, 672 families, and 1495 genera. The most abundant phyla across all nine pedoclimatic regions were Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Acidobacteria (Figure 1.1). Proteobacteria was the most abundant phylum for most regions, the only exceptions being the Mediterranean North and Mediterranean South regions, where Actinobacteria was the most abundant phylum. In accordance with previous studies of soil microbiomes, bacteria outnumbered archaea in all regions, with the lowest relative abundance of archaea in the Boreal region (0.47%) and the highest in the continental region (4.15%). Thaumarchaeota was the most abundant archaeal phylum across all regions (Figure A1.1) (Pester et al., 2011).

Figure 1.1. Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant prokaryotic phyla of each pedoclimatic region; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

1.3.2 Alpha-diversity

Prokaryotic alpha diversity at the different regions was assessed by using observed number of unique OTUs and Shannon indices. The observed number of unique OTUs and Shannon indices did not vary much with pedoclimatic region (Figure 1.2). However, there the two Mediterranean regions displayed a lower alpha diversity compared to the more northerly located regions (Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal, Continental, Lusitanian, and Nemoral). The observed difference may be explained by differences in various physio-chemical parameters between the different regions, including pH, temperature, and precipitation, which may significantly affect soil bacterial diversity (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2016; Tan et al., 2020).

Figure 1.2. Observed number of OTUs (Observed) and Shannon indices (Shannon) between pedoclimatic regions. Each colour corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Agricultural management system (conventional vs. organic) did not have any clear impact on the prokaryotic alpha diversity, although conventional fields at the Nemoral region had a significantly higher diversity than organic fields based on Shannon indices (Figure 1.3 and 1.4). If only bacterial OTUs (i.e., no Archaeal OTUs) were included in the analysis, a higher number of observed OTUs was present at the organically managed fields of the Mediterranean South region compared to the conventionally managed ones (Figure A1.2). For the bacterial Shannon indices, a significantly lower diversity was found for the organically managed fields at the Atlantic North, Continental, and Nemoral regions compared to corresponding conventionally managed fields (Figure A1.3).

Figure 1.3. Average number of observed OTUs between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue. Significant differences in values were obtained with t-test (p -values: **** <0.0001, *** <0.001, ** <0.01, * <0.05).

1.3.3 Beta-diversity

The prokaryotic community composition was highly clustered by the different pedoclimatic regions, suggesting that the prokaryotic community composition was shaped by environmental properties unique for each region (Figure 1.5). In general, regions located geographically adjacent to each other tended to group more closely together, indicating that environmental properties correlated to geography played a key role in shaping the prokaryotic communities. For instance, the neighboring regions Mediterranean North and Mediterranean South, grouped together closely and appeared well separated from the remaining regions. A similar trend was observed when only examining the bacterial community composition, i.e. no Archaeal OTUs included (Figure A1.4). Moreover, when examining the Archaeal community composition, the pedoclimatic region also seemed to be a significant driver, however, the Mediterranean regions tended to group more closely with the Pannonian region compared to when the bacterial community was included in the analysis (Figure A1.5). The primary significant impact of the pedoclimatic regions on the prokaryotic community compositions is not surprising as pedoclimatic conditions vary greatly across regions (Staddon et al.,

1998; Lin et al., 2021). Agricultural management system (conventional vs. organic) appeared to have a smaller effect on the prokaryotic community composition for most regions, although some differences were observed. In particular, a distinct separation between management systems was observed for the Atlantic North and Boreal regions, suggesting that management system may play a key role in shaping the prokaryotic community composition at these particular regions.

Figure 1.4. Average Shannon indices between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue. Significant differences in values were obtained with t-test (p -values: **** < 0.0001, *** < 0.001, ** < 0.01, * < 0.05).

The impact of the pedoclimatic region on the prokaryotic community composition was statistically verified using a PERMANOVA analysis (Table 1.3), revealing that the pedoclimatic regions could explain 75 % of the observed variance in the prokaryotic community composition. Agricultural management system only had a minor but significant impact on the prokaryotic community composition. When investigating the bacterial and archaeal communities separate from each other, the pedoclimatic region was a significant driver for shaping both communities, while the agricultural management system only had a significant impact on the bacterial community composition, but not on the archaeal community composition (Table A1.1, Table A1.2).

Figure 1.5. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the prokaryotic OTU composition of the different pedoclimatic regions. The specific regions are indicated by colour; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system is indicated by shape with circles being conventional (conv) and triangles being organic (org) farming.

TABLE 1.3.

SOURCE	F	R2	P
Region	75.2417	0.74725	0.001
Management	2.5016	0.00311	0.038
Region & Management	3.8866	0.03860	0.001
Residuals		0.21104	

Table 1.3. Results of PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of region, management (organic or conventional management) and the interaction between them on the prokaryotic OTU composition. Differences are considered significant if $p \leq 0.05$.

1.3.4 Differential abundant bacterial taxa

To further explore differences in prokaryotic compositions between agricultural management systems and to discover indicator taxa for each system, a differential abundance analysis at the bacterial OTU level was conducted. Several bacterial OTUs were significantly associated with

agricultural management systems at each region (Fig A1.6 to A1.14). For instance, in the Atlantic Central region (Figure A1.6.), several OTUs belonging to the Proteobacteria phylum were significantly associated with conventional farming (genera *Aestuariicella*, *Asticcacaulis*, *Odysella*, *Cystobacter*, *Haliangium*, *Luteibacter*, *Luteimonas*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Nannocystis*, *Pseudoxanthomonas*, *Rhizomicrobium*, and *Stenotrophomonas*), although some also were enriched by the organic farming system, such as two OTUs belonging to the *Geobacter* genus, which is involved in anaerobic respiration (Reguera et al., 2005). The highest number of differential abundant OTUs were seen at the Atlantic North (1041 differential OTUs) and Boreal (1244 differential OTUs) regions (Figure A1.7 and Fig A1.8), suggesting that the agricultural management system has a clear impact on the soil bacterial community in these specific regions. The impact of agricultural management system at these two regions corresponds well to the observed beta diversity (Figure 1.5.), where a clear clustering was seen between conventional and organic farming system. In contrast, only 22 OTUs were differentially abundant at the Pannonian region, suggesting that agricultural management system only has a limited impact on the bacterial community in this region or that the variability between sampled fields is large (Figure A1.14). No clear association between specific genera and agricultural management systems was observed when comparing all regions, although some genera appeared differentially abundant in many of the regions, such as the genus *Gemmatimonas* (differentially abundant in Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal, Continental, Lusitanian, Mediterranean South and Nemoral). Overall, agricultural management system appeared to have varying effects on the microbial communities across the different regions, indicating that the regions may implement the two types of management differently.

1.3.5 amoA gene abundance

Figure 1.6 shows the average *amoA* gene abundance between regions. The abundance of this gene was significantly higher in the Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal, Nemoral, and Pannonian regions, whereas it was lower in the Continental, Lusitanian, Mediterranean North, and Mediterranean South regions. Latitude, translated into higher temperatures in the southern regions, seems to be, at least partially, one of the factors explaining these differences. However, further investigation of soil physicochemical parameters, particularly in the Continental and Pannonia regions, should be carried out to be able to understand these changes.

Figure 1.7 depicts the average *amoA* gene abundance between agricultural management systems (conventional vs organic) in each of the pedoclimatic regions. The *amoA* gene content was significantly higher in conventional farming systems in the Atlantic North ($p < 0.05$), Continental ($p < 0.01$), Mediterranean North ($p < 0.0001$), Mediterranean South ($p < 0.0001$), and Nemoral ($p < 0.05$) regions. This trend was observed in most of the studied regions. Organic farming, not only not leading to larger ammonia oxidizing bacteria communities, but in fact selecting against putative AOBs (*Nitrosospora*, *Nitrosopumilus*) has previously been reported (Chen et al., 2020; Kong et al., 2010).

Figure 1.6. Average *amoA* gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between regions ($p < 0.0001$). The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 1.7. Average *amoA* gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue.

1.3.6 *nirK* gene abundance

Figure 1.8 shows the average *nirK* gene abundance between regions. The abundance of this gene was significantly higher in the the Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal, Lusitanian, Nemoral, and Pannonian regions, whereas it was lower in the Continental, Mediterranean North, and Mediterranean South regions. The Mediterranean North and the Mediterranean South regions were the ones presenting the lowest abundance of this gene. Climatic factors seem to be playing a determining role in these changes, although the results should be further investigated and contrasted with soil physicochemical properties to be fully understood.

Figure 1.8. Average *nirK* gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between regions ($p < 0.0001$). The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

The *nirK* gene content was found to be significantly higher under organic regimes in the Lusitanian ($p < 0.01$), Mediterranean South ($p < 0.0001$), Nemoral ($p < 0.05$), and Pannonian ($p < 0.01$) (Figure 1.9). This tendency was observed in all the regions except for the Mediterranean North. These findings are no aligned with recent studies that have found that both abundance and diversity of nitrite reducing populations were influenced primarily by the phase of the crop rotation and secondarily by growing seasons rather than by agricultural management systems (Han et al., 2020; Maul et al., 2019).

Figure 1.9. Average *nirK* gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue.

1.3.7 *narG* gene abundance

Figure 1.10 shows the average *narG* gene abundance between regions. The abundance of this gene was significantly higher in the the Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal, Continental, Nemoral, and Pannonian regions, whereas it was lower in the Lusitanian, Mediterranean North, and Mediterranean South regions. Unlike the *nirK* gene abundance, the Mediterranean North and Mediterranean South regions presented the lowest abundances. Similarly to the rest of the functional genes, it seems that climatic conditions are the major cause of these changes.

Agricultural management system did not significantly alter the *narG* gene content in any of the regions (Figure 1.11).

Figure 1.10. Average *narG* gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between regions ($p < 0.0001$). The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 1.11. Average *narG* gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue.

1.3.8 *cbbL* gene abundance

The abundance of the *cbbL* red-like gene was significantly higher in the the Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal, Lusitanian, Nemoral and Pannonian regions (Figure 1.12), whereas it was lower in the Continental, Mediterranean North, and Mediterranean South regions. Like with the *nirK* and *narG* genes abundances, the Mediterranean North and Mediterranean South regions presented, once again, the lowest abundances.

The *cbbL* red-like gene abundance was not significantly changed by agricultural management system (Figure 1.13) nor followed a tendency of being affected in a similar by the agricultural systems.

1.3.9 *GH7* gene abundance

Figure 1.14 shows the average *GH7* gene abundance between regions. The abundance of this gene was significantly higher in the Lusitanian regions and lower in the Mediterranean North, and Mediterranean South regions.

Agricultural management systems did not significantly alter the *cbbL* red-like gene content in any of the pedoclimatic regions (Figure 1.15) similarly to the *cbbL* red-like gene, this parameter did not seem to followed any trend among the farming management.

Figure 1.12. Average *cbbL* red-like gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between regions ($p < 0.0001$). The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 1.13. Average *cbbL* red-like gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue.

Figure 1.14. Average GH7 gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between regions ($p < 0.0001$). The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 1.15. Average GH7 gene log copies g^{-1} dry soil between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue.

1.3.10 Overall gene abundances

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of all the functional gene abundances across the different pedoclimatic regions (Figure 1.16) shows four clear distinct clusters. One of the clusters is formed by regions Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal, Nemoral and Pannonian. Another one by the Lusitanian region, the third one by the Continental region, and the fourth one consists of both the Mediterranean North and the Mediterranean South regions. It should be noticed how the clusters including the Northern regions is the most compacted one, while the other samples show a greater dispersion. The reason why the Continental region seems to cluster near the Mediterranean regions, a trend present in the abundances of all the functional genes except for the narG gene (although likely related to lower overall precipitation than in the other regions), should be further investigated.

Figure 1.16. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of all the functional gene abundances across the different pedoclimatic regions. The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system is indicated by shape with circles being conventional (conv) and triangles being organic (org) farming.

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2 Fungal diversity

2.1 Introduction

Fungi play important roles in maintaining essential ecosystem services in agroecosystems. There seems to be consensus that high ratios of fungi to bacteria usually lead to carbon accumulation and less CO₂ being released into the atmosphere (Bailey et al., 2002). Typically, in soil, fungi form dense networks of hyphae which physically binds soil particles and thus preserve soil structure. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) form symbiotic relationships with 72% of the vascular plant species worldwide (Brundrett, 2017). They produce a sticky glomalin glycoprotein, (Wright and Upadhyaya, 1996), which forms aggregates with soil particles and makes AMF important in erosion control (Augé, 2001; Caravaca et al., 2002; Rillig 2004a; Rillig 2004b; Rillig and Mummey, 2006). In addition, AMF are also known to promote plant growth (Gianinazzi et al., 2010; Njeru et al., 2015; Cozzolino et al., 2016), protect plants from various diseases (Solaiman et al., 2014), and help plants to cope with water deficit (Bowles et al., 2016). In turn, saprotrophic soil fungi function as chemical engineers (Turbé et al., 2010) having a major role in decomposing soil organic matter and recycling of carbon and other nutrients.

However, the soil fungal community contains also harmful organisms which benefit from crop residues remaining on the soil surface. These include for example soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi such as species in genus *Fusarium* species which are among the most important pathogenic fungi of cereals and maize worldwide (Yli-Mattila, 2010). They produce mycotoxins that reduce the quality and quantity of crop yield and lead to economic losses and affect the usability of the contaminated crops for food and feed production (Ferrigo et al., 2016).

Different farming systems and management practices may largely impact the soil fungal community. Organic farming incorporate crop rotations including leguminous plants. Furthermore, synthetic fertilizers and pesticides are prohibited. Thus, organic farming has positive impacts on the biodiversity of soil microbiota (Tuomisto et al., 2012; Postma et al., 2008). Recent studies have reported increase of fungal diversity or changes in community composition due to management practises of organic farming (Harkes et al., 2019; Peltoniemi et al., 2021).

Mechanical disturbance such as conventional deep tillage is generally assumed to affect more fungi than bacteria, since the fungal hyphal networks are disrupted. Indeed, fungi seem to dominate over bacteria in no-tillage systems (Hendrix et al., 1986) and reduced tillage may support a high diversity of AMF (Säle et al., 2015). Furthermore fungal hyphal length is shortened under tillage regimes (Oehl et al., 2004), and tillage has been proposed to be a major stress factor leading to a decrease in fungal inoculum potential (e.g., Jasper et al., 1991; Usuki et al., 2007; Al-Karaki, 2013).

Thus, various management practices that are commonly applied in organic and conventional farming systems are suspected to impact on the diversity of fungi in agroecosystems. In this report we aim to explore what is the overall diversity and community composition of soil fungi under organic and conventional farming systems in European agricultural soils representing nine different pedoclimatic regions.

2.2 Material and Methods

2.2.1 DNA extractions and sequencing

The DNA was extracted and sequenced according to protocol described in the Handbook (Lloret et al., 2020). Briefly, for soil DNA extraction, we used the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen) with some modifications. Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen) and NanoDrop 2000c (ThermoFisher Scientific) were employed for subsequent DNA quantification and purity assessment. Purification of the obtained DNA was performed with NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select (Macherey-Nagel).

Fungal amplicon sequencing was carried out by All Genetics & Biology SL (www.allgenetics.eu). The fungal Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region was used for sequencing with the protocol described in the Earth Microbiome Project (<http://www.earthmicrobiome.org/protocols-and-standards/its/>). The libraries were prepared following a 2-step PCR protocol. For library preparation, a fragment of the ITS1 genomic region (of around 300 bp) was amplified using the primers ITS1f (5' CTT GGT CAT TTA GAG GAA GTA A 3') (modified from White et al., 1990) and ITS2 (5' GCT GCG TTC TTC ATC GAT GC 3') (White et al., 1990). These primers included the Illumina sequencing primer sequences attached to their 5' ends. PCRs were carried out in a final volume of 25 µl, containing 2.5 µl of template DNA, 0.5 µM of the primers, 12.5 µl of Supreme NZYtaq 2x Green Master Mix (NZYTech), and ultrapure water up to 25 µl. The reaction mixture was incubated as follows: an initial denaturation step at 95 °C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s, 47 °C for 45 s, 72 °C for 30 s, and a final extension step at 72 °C for 10 min.

The oligonucleotide indices which are required for multiplexing different libraries in the same sequencing pool were attached in a second PCR round with identical conditions but only 5 cycles and 60 °C as the annealing temperature. A negative control that contained no DNA (BPCR) was included in every PCR round to check for contamination during library preparation. The libraries were run on 2 % agarose gels stained with GreenSafe (NZYTech) and imaged under UV light to verify the library size. Libraries were purified using the Mag-Bind RXNPure Plus magnetic beads (Omega Biotek), following the instructions provided by the manufacturer. Then, libraries were pooled in equimolar amounts according to the quantification data provided by the Qubit dsDNA HS Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific). This pool also contained a testimonial amount (1 µl) of the of the PCR negative controls (BPCR2, BPCR4, and BPCR5). The pool was sequenced in a MiSeq PE300 run (Illumina). Sequencing

was conducted with the Illumina MiSeq system with a read length of 2 x 300 bp and an output of 22-25 M reads. Median sample library size was 173 973 reads.

2.2.2 Bioinformatics

Fungal ITS1 sequences were assembled, quality filtered, and pre-processed along with chimera filtering, clustering and taxonomical annotations with a PipeCraft 1.0 pipeline (Anslan et al., 2017). PipeCraft utilizes several implemented tools of e.g. mothur v1.36.1 (Schloss et al., 2009), vsearch v1.11.1, and CD-HIT v4.6 (Fu et al., 2012). Raw sequence reads were processed according to the manual, with slight modifications for demultiplexed sequence data. Briefly, assembly of paired-end reads and initial quality filtering was conducted with vsearch (v1.11.1; github.com/torognes/vsearch; Rognes et al., 2016) according to the following parameters: minimum overlap 15; max differences 99; minimum length 150 bp; e_max 1; max ambiguous 0 and trunc qual 20. On average, 60 % of the raw reads were filtered out after the assembly. Chimera filtering was performed for the reoriented reads using reference-based filtering with Unite ITS1 ref. v7.1 as a database and vsearch de novo filtering with parameters: annotation 0.97 and abskew 2. Primers and primer artifacts were also filtered out from sequences at this step. In addition, fungal ITS1 region was extracted from reads with ITSx (Bengtsson-Palme et al., 2013). In the next step, sequence reads were clustered and OTU table created with CD-hit with parameters: threshold 0.97; and min size 2. In the last step, OTUs were taxonomically annotated by searching for representative sequences with BLAST using the reference ITS1 database (sh_genral_release_dynamic_02.02.2019.fasta) from UNITE (Nilsson et al., 2018) was used. After the first filtering steps, raw sequence data consisted of 11 394 518 reads clustering into 28 027 OTUs.

Secondary filtering was done based on the results of the BLAST and the alignments: We filtered out all OTUs which did not match to fungal sequences in databases, those with identity below 70% to fungi, and rare OTUs that were observed less than 11 times in the whole data (0.001% of the total read amount). This resulted in 11 047 626 fungal reads that were affiliated to 7750 OTUs. The final data consisted of 188 separate sample libraries with median library size 60 198 reads varying from 26 771 to 85 131 reads.

2.2.3 Community and statistical analyses

All analyses were conducted in R version 3.6.0 or 3.6.1 (R core Team 2018) and R studio (version 1.2.5001). All figures were made using 'phyloseq' (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) and 'ggplot2' (Wickham, 2016) R packages. Alpha-diversity were determined from the raw data and beta-diversity from the proportional data (relative abundance of OTU reads from the total read amount of the sample library). For the analysis of AMF data, we used geometric mean of pairwise ratios

normalization (GMPR; Chen et al., 2018) which deals with zero-inflated community data and preserves differences in relative abundances of taxa.

Alpha-diversity including richness (observed number of OTUs) and Shannon index were obtained with 'microbiome' R package (Lahti et al., 2017). Significant differences between regions and agricultural management systems (conventional vs. organic) were investigated with linear mixed models (LMMs).

Beta-diversity was investigated by using nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) with stable solution from random starts, axis scaling and species scores with function metaMDS from 'vegan' package 2.5-5 (Oksanen et al., 2019) by using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index. We did permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) using distance matrices with function adonis from vegan package to test the effect of region and agricultural management system (conventional vs. organic) to fungal community composition. Venn graph to find out the proportion of the shared and specific OTUs for agricultural management systems were conducted with 'ps_venn' with the script ps_venn.R found in <https://zenodo.org/record/4733747>.

To identify taxa that were significantly associated with different agricultural management systems, we conducted a differential abundance analysis using the *ancombc* function of the ANCOMBC package (Lin and Peddada, 2020) for each region. The analysis was conducted at the OTU level using the default settings except for the following; zero_cut=0.75, lib_cut=1000, struc_zero=TRUE, conserve=TRUE.

FUNGuild, the online application tool, was used to detect functional information, fungal guilds of OTUs (Nguyen et al., 2016). The general effect of Pedoclimatic region and agricultural management system (conventional vs. organic) on relative proportion of reads representing different functional fungal groups from the whole data was investigated with generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs). Region, management and their interaction were used as explanatory (fixed) factors. The Tukey-Kramer method was used in pairwise comparisons of class means for categorical fixed factors. For generalizing the modelling results to the data population, the average model predictions with their 95% confidence intervals were calculated using only the explanatory (fixed) factors. The mixed model analyses were performed with the GLIMMIX procedure of the SAS statistical software (version 9.4). Additionally, a SAS macro was used to display results with letters in pairwise comparisons (Piepho, 2012).

2.3 Results and discussion

2.3.1 Taxonomic profiles

In general, most of the reads (11% from all reads) showed the closest match to ascomycete *Acremonium furcatum* and 9% to a six species cluster of the genus *Mortierella* (data not shown). The dominant OTUs belonged to phyla Ascomycota, Basidiomycota, Chytridiomycota and

Mortierellomycota and unidentified fungal sequences without clear affiliation to any known phylum (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. Five of the most dominant fungal phyla in regions by agricultural management system. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Figure 2.2. Ten of the most dominant fungal class in regions by agricultural management system. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Sordariomycetes was the most abundant fungal class in all regions, and Tremellomyces, Mortierellomycetes and Dothideomycetes were the second most abundant fungal classes. (Figure

2.2). The proportion of Mortierellomycetes was abundant in the fields of the Nemoral region and that of Dothideomycetes in the fields of the Mediterranean regions.

Venn analysis showed that 85% of the OTUs were present both in the fields under conventional and organic farming (data not shown). Only 5 and 10 % of fungal OTUs were unique and detected only from the fields under conventional or organic farming, respectively. This it seems that most of the fungi are common for both agricultural management systems and only a minority represent the community that is affected by differences in the field under conventional and organic farming systems.

2.3.2 Alpha-diversity

Observed number of OTUs (Figure 2.3) were significantly higher in the Nemoral region compared the Pannonian and two Mediterranean regions, and lower in the Mediterranean South region compared to two Atlantic, and Boreal, Lusitanian and Nemoral regions. In turn, Shannon index (Figure 2.1) was higher in the Pannonian region compared to other regions except the Nemoral and Mediterranean North regions. These regions differ from each other by their pedoclimatic factors (e.g. temperature and precipitation) which likely explains the result. However, soil fungi in the fields of the Pannonian region seem to be more diverse compared to others, but the reason for this must be further investigated.

Figure 2.3. Average alpha measures (observed number OTUs and Shannon index) of regions. Significant differences between regions are shown in letters according to LMM. The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

When richness estimates and diversity indices were investigated by agricultural management systems in each region separately, both observed number of OTUs and Shannon index were higher in the fields under organic farming in the Lusitanian and Nemoral and regions (Figure 2.4). Whether the increase is linked to management practices conducted in the fields under organic system in these regions must be further investigated.

Figure 2.4. Average number of a) observed OTUs and b) Shannon index between agricultural management systems in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system of the farms is indicated by colour with conventional (conv) farms being red and organic (org) farms being blue. Significant differences in values were obtained with LMM (p -values: **** <0.0001, *** <0.001, ** <0.01, * <0.05).

2.3.3 Beta-diversity

Soil fungal communities of the two Mediterranean regions, as well as those of the Pannonian and Lusitanian regions are distinct from those of other regions (Figure 2.5), whereas communities of Atlantic, Continental, Nemoral and Boreal regions are more similar with each other. Region itself explains about 40% differences in the soil fungal community, but management type (conventional or organic farming) only very little (Table 2.1). This indicates that the simple comparison between regions and conventional and organic farming systems is not enough to explain all the changes that will impact soil fungal community composition and diversity in different regions. A further investigation on the impacts of different management practices and soil chemical and physical factors on the soil fungal community composition and diversity is needed.

Figure 2.5. NMDS (non-metric multidimensional scaling) from fungal ITS OTU data. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by region and symbols by farming type. Ellipses show the confidence interval of the mean according to separations by regions. The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system is indicated by shape with circles being conventional (conv) and triangles being organic (org) farming.

TABLE 2.1

SOURCE	F	R2	P
Management	4.9691	0.01516	0.001
Region	16.5529	0.40413	0.001
Region & management	2.5357	0.06191	0.001
Residuals		0.51880	

Table 2.1. Results of PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of region, agricultural management system (organic or conventional) or both on fungal OTU composition. Differences are considered significant if $p \leq 0.05$.

2.3.4 Differentially abundance fungal taxa

Differential abundance with ANCOM-BC analysis did reveal variable amounts of indicative OTUs for the fields under conventional or organic farming systems depending on the region (Figures A2.1a-i). Only a few indicative OTUs were obtained from the Atlantic Central and Boreal regions (Figures A2.1a and A2.1c). In the Atlantic Central region (Figure A2.1a), only one indicative OTU representing unknown genus of the Ascomycota phylum (closest similarity to the *Xylariales* order) was observed and it was significantly associated to the organic management. Whereas in the Boreal region two OTU representing the Ascomycota (genus *Leptodiscella* and unknown with closest similarity to the *Sordariomycetes* class) were associated with organic management. The highest number of differential abundant OTUs were seen at Mediterranean North (65 differential OTUs) and South (97 differential OTUs) regions, and Lusitanian (85 differential OTUs) region (Figures A2.1e-g) suggesting that the agricultural management system has a clear impact on the soil fungal community in these specific regions.

There were over two times more OTUs that were indicative for the fields under organic farming (26 OTUs) than those under conventional farming (12 OTUs) in the Atlantic North region (Figure A2.1a). All indicative OTUs associated to organic management belong to the Ascomycota phylum and the classes of Eurotiales, Dothideomycetes, Leotiomyces and Sordariomycetes. These included orders Hypocreales (genera *Acremonium*, *Dactylonectria*, *Fusarium*, *Metarhizium*), Sordariales (genus *Remersonia*), Glomerellales (*Plectopshaerella*), Pleosporales (genera *Boeremia*, *Didymella*, *Paraphaeosphaeria*, *Torula*), Helotiales (genus *Cadophora*), and Eurotiales (genera *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*). For example, *Metarhizium* include animal pathogens, and *Cadophora* dark septate endophytes from plant roots. Pleosporales is the largest order in the fungal class Dothideomycetes which are mainly saprotrophs, but also include parasites, epi- and endophytes. It has been suggested that organic farming practices would increase the abundance and species diversity of plant-associated endophytic fungi such as those that belong to Pleosporales and Hypocreales which have potential to improve plant yields and health (Xia et al., 2019). In turn, OTUs typical for conventional farming included, for example, genera *Lecythophora* containing dark septate endophytes from plant roots, unknown saprotrophic genera *Articulospora* and *Eucasphaeria*, as well as pathogenic genera *Haptocillium* and *Tetragoniomyces*. It appears that organic farming in the fields of the North Atlantic region may have promoted the abundance of fungi with a wide functional diversity from plant health promoters (saprotrophs and endophytes) to parasites and pathogens.

In the Continental region two indicative OTUs for the fields under organic farming belong to Ascomycota phylum including genus *Dactylonectria* and unknown genus with closest similarity to the Pleosporales order (Figure A2.1d). Genus *Dactylonectria* contains representatives capable of acting in multiple roles as pathogens, endophytes and saprotrophs. Whereas, for instance, indicative OTUs in the fields under conventional farming represented saprotrophic genera *Sclerostagonospora* (order Pleosporales) and *Byssochlamys* (order Eurotiales) of the Ascomycota phylum as well as parasitic and saprotrophic yeast genus *Sporobolomyces* of the Basidiomycota phylum.

In the Lusitanian region 16 and 68 indicative OTUs were observed from the fields under organic and conventional farming, respectively (Figure A2.1e). OTUs indicative for organic farming showed taxonomically and functionally diverse set of fungi. Almost all of them belonged to Ascomycota phylum and its classes Eurotiomycetes, Dothideomycetes, Leotiomycetes and Sordariomycetes. These included for instance OTUs that belong to known fungal endophytic taxa *Cadophora* and *Chaetomium*. The former contains dark septate endophytes (DSE) which produce dark melanized hyphae and found inside plant roots or in rhizosphere soil (Berthelot et al., 2019). DSE can be found from diverse range of ecosystems and host plants and have wide taxonomic and functional variety, and they provide nutrients for plants from soil organic matter (SOM), protect plants from pathogens and harsh soil conditions (Berthelot et al., 2019). Because of their ability to produce highly melanized and recalcitrant hyphae, DSE could have important role in C sequestration into more stable SOM (Siletti et al., 2017). Other OTUs indicative for organic farming included pathogenic or parasitic genera *Metarhizium*, *Neonectria* and *Tolypocladium*, saprotrophic genus *Dichotomopilus*. Whereas OTUs indicative for conventional farming included for instance well-known pathogenic genus *Fusarium*, and many saprotrophic genera (e.g., *Apiotrichum*, *Articulospora*, *Cladophialophora*, *Emericellopsis*, *Gymnoascus*, *Petriella*). Overall, the results suggest that factors related to different agricultural management system in Lusitanian regions may have promoted abundances of fungi with diverse roles indicating high fungal functional diversity in soil.

In the Mediterranean North region, most of the indicator OTUs (90 % of indicator OTUs) were associated to organic farming referring to distinct fungal community in the field compared to those of under conventional farming (Figure A2.1f). Many OTUs indicative to organic farming belong to Ascomycota phylum including many saprotrophs associated to dung (*Arachnomyces*, *Coprinus*, *Podospora*, *Stillbella*, *Thielavia*). Indicators included also an OTU related to endophytic genus *Chaetomium* and three other OTUs belonging to Glomeromycota phylum affiliating to arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal (AMF) genera *Diversispora* and *Claroideoglossum*. These indicator taxa may refer to differences in management practices, since organic farming most often utilizes manure as organic fertilizer and implements reduced tillage or non-tillage practices which may favour the abundance of AMF (Kabir, 2005, Dai et al., 2015).

In the Mediterranean South region there were 28 and 68 indicative OTUs in the fields under organic and conventional farming, respectively (Figure A2.1g). Many indicative OTUs for organic farming were not identified to genus level, but showed, for example, closest relation to order Pleosporales, class Sordariomycetes and family *Nectriaceae*. However, they included OTUs that belong to undefined saprotrophs (*Lophiotrema*), dung saprotrophs (*Schizothecium*), and genera with common pathogens (*Alternaria*, *Gibberella*, *Mycosphaerella*, *Nectria*). Whereas OTUs indicative for conventional farming with identified function for example included many undefined saprotrophic genera (*Botryotrichum*, *Iodophanus*, *Parascenodosporium*, *Pithoascus*, *Preussia*, *Rhizophlyctis*, *Trichophaeopsis*), pathogenic genera (*Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*) and endophytic *Chaetomium/Chaetomiaceae*. Both farming management systems in the Mediterranean South region seem to increase the abundance of fungi with varying functional roles, which makes the final interpretation difficult.

In the Nemoral region (Figure A2.1h) only 7 indicative OTUs for the fields under organic farming belonged for instance to taxa containing dung saprotrophs and endophytes *Podospora* and harmless parasite of wheat roots *Rhizopydium*. Interestingly there was also an OTU belonging to the Basidiomycota phylum and the Sebacinales order. Endophytic Sebacinales are commonly found from roots in agricultural soils and reported to be more prevalent in wheat roots from the field under organic management (Riess et al., 2014; Verbruggen et al., 2014). Thus, this result further verifies that Sebacinales is an indicative taxa for organic management.

In the Pannonian region (Figure A2.1i) OTUs indicative for the fields under organic farming include for instance genera *Trichoderma* and *Fusarium*. Interestingly the species of *Trichoderma* are known to be effective biocontrolling agents against pathogenic *Fusarium* and act as biofertilizers for plant growth promotion (Sharma, 2011; Sharma et al., 2019). This finding an indicative example about the natural interactions of beneficial and harmful fungi which might be affected by farming management system.

2.3.5 Functional fungal guilds

An average over third (35%) of the OTUs could not be defined to any fungal functional guild. From those that were functionally defined, the dominant guild was pathotrophs-saprotrophs-symbiotrophs (22% of all OTUs), and equal amounts (17%) were defined as saprotrophs-symbiotrophs and saprotrophs guilds, respectively (Figure 2.6). Pathotrophs (5%), pathotrophs-saprotrophs (3%), symbiotrophs (0.6%) and pathotrophs-symbiotrophs (0.3%) were minor guilds.

The proportion of saprotrophs did not differ between regions (Table 2.2). Whereas, the proportion of pathotrophs was significantly bigger in the Atlantic Central compared to the Continental region. In turn, proportion of symbiotrophs was bigger in the Nemoral region compared to other regions except for the Boreal and Mediterranean South regions. The proportion of saprotrophs-pathotrophs was bigger in the Continental and Nemoral regions compared to Lusitanian and Mediterranean South regions. The proportion of saprotrophs-symbiotrophs was bigger in the Nemoral regions compared to other regions except for the Atlantic North region.

The proportion of saprotrophs was bigger in the fields under conventional farming compared to organic farming in the Lusitanian region (Figure 2.7). There was a clear difference in the abundance of the most dominant saprotrophic orders in the fields under different agricultural management systems in the Lusitanian region which likely explain the result (Figure 2.8). There was distinctively more OTUs that belong to the order Pezizales in the family *Pyrenemataceae* and its genus *Pseudaleuria*. *Pseudaleuria* contains undefined saprotroph and they have been reported to enrich in the acidic agricultural soil treated with inorganic-organic fertilization (NPKM) (Ning et al., 2020).

Figure 2.6. Distribution of functional fungal guilds according to FunGuild in different regions. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, Pat = pathotroph, Sap = saprotroph, Sym = symbiotroph.

TABLE 2.2

	SAP	PAT	SYM	SAP-PAT	PAT-SYM	SAP-SYM	PAT-SAP-SYM	UNDEFINED
atl_cent	15.5 a	6.9 a	0.3 cd	2.5 ab	0.1 c	13.8 c	32.9 a	28.0 b
atl_north	17.2 a	5.0 ab	0.4 bc	4.1 ab	0.1 c	30.8 ab	16.3 bc	26.0 b
boreal	17.0 a	5.3 ab	0.7 ab	3.3 ac	0.2 bc	16.0 c	17.5 bc	40.0 a
cont	13.5 a	3.4 b	0.2 d	3.9 a	0.1 c	18.6 bc	33.9 a	26.4 b
lusit	19.4 a	4.6 ab	0.6 bc	1.3 c	0.5 ab	13.9 c	19.1 bc	40.7 a
med_north	19.7 a	7.1 ab	0.4 bc	3.5 ab	0.3 ac	10.9 c	17.9 bc	40.3 b
med_south	19.7 a	7.4 ab	0.6 ab	1.6 bc	0.3 ac	3.8 d	16.1 c	50.6 a
nemoral	12.1 a	4.8 ab	1.1 a	4.4 a	0.2 ac	36.5 a	20.3 bc	20.7 b
pann	16.6 a	3.6 ab	1.0 ab	3.3 ab	0.9 a	10.9 c	24.0 ab	39.6 a

Table 2.2. The mean proportions (%) of fungal functional guilds between different regions. Letters represent statistically different groups. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, Pat = pathotroph, Sap = saprotroph, Sym = symbiotroph.

Figure 2.7. The mean proportion of saprotrophs (sap) regions in the fields under the conventional (conv) or organic (org) farming. Asterisks show significant differences between agricultural management systems. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 2.8. The abundance of the most dominant saprotrophic orders in regions by agricultural management systems. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

The proportion of pathotrophs was bigger under the organic farming in South Mediterranean region (Figure 2.9). Abundance of certain pathotrophic taxa may explain the result, since fungal OTUs of the

pathotrophic order Capnodiales were much more abundant in the South Mediterranean region under the fields under organic farming (Figure 2.10). OTUs of this order belong to the largest genus of common plant pathogenic genera *Mycosphaerella* which include the causal agents of several economically important crop and tree diseases. Thus, this result may indicate that organic farming along with warm and dry climate of the South Mediterranean region may benefit these fungi.

Figure 2.9. The mean proportion of pathotrophs (pat) between the conventional (conv) or organic (org) farming in different regions. Asterisks show significant differences between agricultural management systems. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

The proportion of symbiotrophs was bigger under the organic farming in the Lusitanian region (Figure 2.11). There was a clear difference in the abundance of the most dominant symbiotrophic orders between agricultural management systems in the Lusitanian region which likely explain the result (Figure 2.12). There was distinctively more OTUs that belong to the orders of Helotiales and Coniochaetales and their genera *Phialocephala*, *Cadophora* and *Lecythophora*. These genera contain dark septate endophytes (DSE) which inhabit plant roots which frequently co-occur with other mycorrhizal fungi (Mandyam and Jumpponen, 2005). The majority of DSE studied have shown that inoculation of DSE increased total, root, and shoot biomass of host plant by up to 80% (Newsham, 2011). DSE can increase nitrogen and phosphorus content in host plant tissue (Jumpponen, 2001; Newsham, 2011), and they are suggested to link between plant roots and soil crusts that fix carbon and nitrogen in hyphal network forming the basis of the Fungal Loop Hypothesis (Porrás-Alfalo et al., 2011). In addition, the melanized cell walls of DSE may affect heat dissipation or form complexes with oxygen radicals, which can alter host thermal tolerance of host plant. Like other mycorrhizal fungi, DSE can protect hosts from pathogens or herbivores through the production of antibacterial or antifungal metabolites, physical exclusion of other microorganisms, or melanized hyphae (Mandyam

and Jumpponen, 2005). Thus, the result would indicate that organic farming in the Lusitanian region has increased the amount of DSE fungi which serve many soil and plant health promoting ecosystem services.

Figure 2.10. The abundance of the most dominant pathotrophic orders in regions by agricultural management systems. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Figure 2.11. The mean proportion of symbiotrophs (sym) in the fields under the conventional (conv) or organic (org) farming in different regions. Asterisks show significant differences between agricultural management systems. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 2.12. The abundance of the most dominant symbiotrophic orders in regions by agricultural management systems. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

2.3.6 The community of AMF

The community of AMF did not show any clustering according to region nor agricultural management system (Figure 2.13). In addition, numbers of AMF derived OTUs community did not differ between agricultural management systems in any region (Figure 2.14). AMF classes varied between regions, and as rare OTUs the presence probably slightly correlated with sequencing depth and could partly explain the low observations in the Pannonian region (Figure 2.15). However, there is still a need to conduct a more detailed investigations about the possible effects of the management practices in the fields of different agricultural management systems to verify their response since AMF are indicators of sustainable ecosystems (Herrick, 2000) and are known to play an important role in agricultural production (Jeffries et al., 2003; Avio et al., 2013).

Figure 2.13. NMDS (non-metric multidimensional scaling) from AMF ITS OTU data. Different colours separate the fungal ITS derived OTUs by region and symbols by farming type. Ellipses show the confidence interval of the mean according to separations by regions. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Figure 2.14. OTU numbers of AMF in the fields under the conventional (conv) or organic (org) farming in different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Asterisks show significant differences between agricultural management systems.

Figure 2.15. Abundance of AMF classes presented as the GMPR normalised number of reads in a sample. Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

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3 Microbial biomass characterization

3.1 Introduction

The biomass of soil microbes, i.e., its abundance, is an important parameter related with soil health because microbes' presence is a key factor for multiple soil functions such as organic matter decomposition, nutrient cycling or biodiversity (Nannipieri et al., 2003; González-Quiñones et al., 2011). The abundance (or biomass) can be interpreted as a measure of microbe's "reservoir" in soils. Thus, maintenance and/or increase of this parameter in soils is of key importance for agricultural sustainability. Microbial abundance may be considered from different points of view: total microbial abundance or abundance of specific groups such as bacteria or fungi. The estimation of the microbial abundance can be performed using different methodologies (Zelles et al., 1994; Martens, 1995). One of these methodologies is the extraction of lipids specific of different groups of microorganisms, such as phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) (Frostegård and Bååth, 1996) or neutral lipid fatty acids (NLFAs) (Ngosong et al., 2012.) that are being employed in SoildiverAgro project.

3.2 Material and Methods

To estimate the abundance of different groups of microbes, the method described by Frostegård and Bååth (1996) was used. Briefly: lipids were extracted from soils using "Bligh and Dyer" solution, and then neutral lipids, glycolipids and phospholipids were separated using silica columns and solvents with different polarity: methanol for neutral lipids, acetone for glycolipids and chloroform for phospholipids. After separation, neutral lipids and phospholipids were subjected to mild alkaline methanolysis (transesterification) to break the lipids and obtain the fatty acids. After this step, the fatty acids were determined by gas chromatography. Different fatty acids are specific of different microbial groups, allowing to calculate the abundance of these groups by summing different fatty acids. Most of microbial groups were estimated using phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) while neutral lipid fatty acid (NLFA) 16:1 ω 5 was used to estimate the abundance of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Table 3.1).

Data normality was checked using Kolmogorov-Smirnov when $n \geq 30$, and Shapiro-Wilk when $n < 30$. The homogeneity of variance was tested using Levene's test. When data were normally distributed, the statistical significance of differences between region and management were estimated using one-way ANOVA, for equal (Bonferroni posthoc test) and no equal variances (Games-Howell posthoc test, which is robust to heteroscedasticity). When data were not normally distributed, we tried to normalize them using log or square root transformations. When transformations did not work, the Kruskal–Wallis test was used for non-normally distributed data expressing equal variance. Based on

statistics recommendations (MacDonald, 2014), one-way ANOVA followed by the Games-Howell posthoc test was used in one particularly challenging case even though data were not normal, and variance was not equal. Different letters (a, b, c, d...) were used to show significant differences between regions. The statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS statistics 25.0. Results which show different letters mean significant differences among each parameter.

TABLE 3.1	
Total abundance	All determined PLFAs
Bacteria	PLFAs: i15:0, a15:0, 15:0, i16:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7t, i17:0, a17:0, 17:0, cy17:0, 18:1 ω 7, cy19:0
Gram-positive Bacteria	PLFAs: br17:0, br18:0, i17:0, a17:0, i16:0, i16:1, 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, i15:0, a15:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7c, 18:1 ω 7 and 19:1
Gram-negative Bacteria	PLFAs: cy17:0, cy19:0, r-hydroxy fatty acids, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7, 16:1 ω 5, 18:1 ω 7 and 19:1
Actinobacteria	PLFAs: 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0 and 10Me18:0
Fungi	PLFA: 18:2 ω 6 (linoleic acid)
Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	NLFAs: 16:1 ω 5

Table 3.1. Fatty acid biomarkers used to estimate the abundance of different microbial groups.

3.3 Results and discussion

3.3.1 Total microbial abundance

The total microbial abundance data (estimated as total PLFAs), classified by region and management practice, are shown in Table 3.2. Overall data ranged between 3.97 and 136.35 nmol g⁻¹ and show significant differences between regions ($F = 63.135$, $P < 0.001$), following the next sequence: Boreal^a \approx Lusitanian^a \approx Continental^a \approx Nemoral^a $>$ Pannonian^b \approx Atlantic Central^b \approx Atlantic North^b $>$ Mediterranean North^c \approx Mediterranean South^c. Analyzing all the data set, significant differences between conventional and organic management systems were not found. When management practices were compared at regional level, in five of these regions significant differences were found for total microbial abundance. However, the results were not consistent, since in some areas microbial abundance was significantly higher in organic than in conventional management practices [Lusitanian ($Z = -2.853$, $P < 0.05$); Nemoral ($t = -2.878$, $P < 0.05$)], while in others the opposite was found [Atlantic North ($t = 4.284$, $P < 0.001$); Mediterranean North ($Z = 2.799$, $P < 0.05$); Pannonian ($t = 2.906$, $P < 0.05$)].

TABLE 3.2

		MEAN	SD	MAX	MIN
Atl_cent	Conv	42.50	16.60	62.62	17.51
	Org	47.22	17.90	76.59	20.52
Atl_north	Conv	43.64	10.52	61.21	30.73
	Org	19.00	14.84	48.20	5.05
Boreal	Conv	95.80	18.57	123.51	71.41
	Org	90.22	18.20	126.81	65.65
Cont	Conv	75.72	16.32	97.60	50.81
	Org	73.07	23.41	115.60	36.27
Lusit	Conv	69.37	14.87	98.22	53.39
	Org	103.90	25.35	136.35	48.38
Med_north	Conv	13.60	6.02	27.22	8.30
	Org	7.82	2.56	12.93	3.97
Med_south	Conv	8.50	1.61	11.62	6.81
	Org	9.03	5.02	22.92	4.92
Nemoral	Conv	59.00	17.02	90.64	37.31
	Org	86.04	24.36	123.50	46.42
Pann	Conv	57.01	9.60	71.77	44.01
	Org	44.24	9.03	58.58	33.90

Table 3.2. Total microbial abundance expressed as total PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹) found for the different pedoclimatic regions and management practices. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

3.3.2 Total bacterial abundance

Bacterial abundance, expressed as bacterial PLFAs, is shown in Table 3.3 for 9 pedoclimatic regions and management practices (organic and conventional). The values varied between 2.81 and 68.43 nmol g⁻¹, showing significant differences in the different regions ($F = 49.071$, $P < 0.001$). The following sequence was found: Boreal^a \approx Lusitanian^a \approx Nemoral^a \approx Continental^a $>$ Pannonian^b \approx Atlantic Central^b \approx Atlantic North^b $>$ Mediterranean North^c \approx Mediterranean South^c. However, management practices did not provide significant differences for Bacterial PLFAs when all data were considered. When management practices were compared at regional level, in four of these regions significant differences were found for bacterial abundance. However, the results were not consistent, since in two areas bacterial abundance was significantly higher in organic than in conventional management practices [Lusitanian ($Z = -2.763$, $P < 0.05$); Nemoral ($t = -2.913$, $P < 0.01$)], while in other two the opposite behaviour was found [Atlantic North ($t = 4.475$, $P < 0.001$); Mediterranean North ($Z = 2.873$, $P < 0.05$)].

TABLE 3.3

		MEAN	SD	MAX	MIN
Atl_cent	Conv	20.72	9.39	36.86	8.24
	Org	23.37	11.11	45.38	8.44
Atl_north	Conv	23.43	4.81	31.28	17.66
	Org	10.94	7.40	24.71	3.65
Boreal	Conv	47.91	10.81	65.34	34.32
	Org	45.97	10.64	67.53	32.22
Cont	Conv	37.60	7.70	49.62	25.61
	Org	35.66	11.74	56.63	16.22
Lusit	Conv	29.33	6.16	41.78	22.15
	Org	49.64	13.17	68.43	20.65
Med_north	Conv	7.04	2.95	13.65	4.50
	Org	5.10	1.18	7.37	3.14
Med_south	Conv	5.02	0.46	5.80	4.42
	Org	4.64	0.74	5.51	2.81
Nemoral	Conv	29.16	10.34	47.39	10.14
	Org	44.93	13.65	66.10	23.11
Pann	Conv	24.45	4.35	31.36	19.14
	Org	20.30	4.45	27.67	14.90

Table 3.3. Total bacterial abundance expressed as sum of bacterial PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹) found for the different pedoclimatic regions and management practices. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

3.3.2.1 Gram-positive bacteria abundance

Gram+ PLFAs results are shown in Table 3.4 as function of pedoclimatic region and management (organic and conventional). Comparing all data, Bacterial Gram+ PLFAs data ranged between 2.03 and 30.31 nmol g⁻¹, showing significant differences among regions ($F = 28.491$ $P < 0.001$) and the next sequence: Boreal^a \geq Lusitanian^{ab} \geq Continental^{bc} \approx Nemoral^{bc} \geq Pannonian^c \approx Atlantic Central^c \approx Atlantic North^c $>$ Mediterranean North^d \approx Mediterranean South^d. However, management practices did not provide significant results using overall data. Considering each region separately, management type was significantly different at Atlantic North ($Z = -3.402$, $P < 0.01$), Lusitanian ($t = -5.380$, $P < 0.001$), Mediterranean South ($t = 2.817$, $P < 0.01$) and Nemoral ($Z = -2.117$, $P < 0.05$). These results are not consistent, since in some cases conventional shows higher values than organic farming practices, but in others the opposite trend was found.

3.3.2.2 Gram-negative bacteria abundance

Gram negative bacteria abundance, expressed as G- bacterial PLFAs, is shown in Table 3.5 for 9 pedoclimatic regions and management practices (organic and conventional), ranging between 0.05 and 37.36 nmol g⁻¹. Analyzing all data, there were significant differences among all regions (F = 62.893, P < 0.001) resulting the next sequence: Boreal^a ≈ Nemoral^a ≈ Lusitanian^a ≈ Continental^a > Pannonian^b ≈ Atlantic Central^b ≈ Atlantic North^b > Mediterranean North^c ≈ Mediterranean South^c. In addition, results didn't show significant differences between management practices analyzing all data set. By analyzing each region separately, there were significantly differences between conventional and organic management systems in Atlantic North (t = 5.344, P < 0.001,), Lusitanian (Z = -2.791, P < 0.01), Mediterranean North (Z = -3.556, P < 0.001), Nemoral (t = -2.258, P < 0.05). However, these results are not consistent, since in one cases conventional show higher value than organic farming practices, but in other three the opposite trend was found.

		TABLE 3.4			
		MEAN	SD	MAX	MIN
Atl_cent	Conv	10.08	5.49	20.14	2.28
	Org	11.18	5.91	21.70	3.36
Atl_north	Conv	10.50	2.73	17.40	8.02
	Org	4.90	1.88	9.73	3.51
Boreal	Conv	20.22	5.04	25.74	13.12
	Org	17.71	4.92	27.00	12.31
Cont	Conv	13.24	2.43	17.84	9.47
	Org	12.14	3.25	17.62	6.47
Lusit	Conv	10.65	2.05	15.02	8.12
	Org	20.14	5.25	30.31	8.36
Med_north	Conv	3.75	1.57	7.22	2.64
	Org	4.05	0.64	5.02	3.05
Med_south	Conv	4.00	0.18	4.37	3.69
	Org	3.35	0.71	4.02	2.03
Nemoral	Conv	8.96	3.97	17.20	5.45
	Org	14.37	6.45	25.15	6.04
Pann	Conv	11.02	1.79	13.62	8.87
	Org	10.25	2.48	14.55	7.39

Table 3.4. Gram-positive bacteria abundance expressed as sum of gram-positive PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹) found for the different pedoclimatic regions and management practices. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

TABLE 3.5

		MEAN	SD	MAX	MIN
Atl_cent	Conv	9.09	3.90	15.67	4.40
	Org	10.16	4.18	18.05	4.46
Atl_north	Conv	11.63	3.12	17.39	8.19
	Org	5.48	5.32	13.34	0.05
Boreal	Conv	24.90	6.12	36.77	18.24
	Org	25.16	5.42	36.33	17.19
Cont	Conv	21.81	5.06	28.45	13.93
	Org	20.82	7.57	34.41	8.57
Lusit	Conv	16.76	3.80	23.73	12.54
	Org	26.54	7.62	35.55	10.76
Med_north	Conv	2.93	1.31	5.85	1.66
	Org	0.91	0.75	2.48	0.05
Med_south	Conv	0.76	0.26	1.25	0.49
	Org	1.13	0.69	2.97	0.59
Nemoral	Conv	18.33	6.46	27.17	4.03
	Org	27.84	6.76	37.36	15.57
Pann	Conv	11.64	2.31	15.42	8.85
	Org	8.79	1.80	11.71	6.56

Table 3.5. Gram-negative bacteria abundance expressed as sum of gram-negative PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹) found for the different pedoclimatic regions and management practices. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

3.3.2.3 Actinobacteria abundance

Actinobacterial abundance, expressed as sum of PLFA markers related with this group is shown in Table 3.6 classified by region and management practices. Actinobacterial abundance ranged between 0.04 and 16.46 nmol g⁻¹. Comparing all data, significant differences were found between regions ($F = 40.692$, $P < 0.001$) and the obtained sequence was Boreal^a ≥ Lusitanian^{ab} ≥ Continental^b ≈ Nemoral^b ≈ Pannonian^b > Atlantic Central^c ≥ Atlantic North^{cd} ≥ Mediterranean North^d ≈ Mediterranean South^d. However, comparing management practices (conventional and organic) overall results did not provide significant differences. Considering each region separately, management type was significantly different at Atlantic North ($Z = 2.873$, $P < 0.01$), Lusitanian ($Z = -3.163$, $P < 0.05$), Mediterranean North ($Z = 3.063$, $P < 0.05$), Nemoral ($t = -2.759$, $P < 0.05$) and Pannonian ($t = 3.132$, $P < 0.01$). However, these results are not consistent, since in 3 cases conventional show higher value than organic farming practices, but in other two the opposite trend was found.

TABLE 3.6

		MEAN	SD	MAX	MIN
Atl_cent	Conv	2.84	2.80	7.52	0.12
	Org	2.92	2.42	6.67	0.12
Atl_north	Conv	4.21	3.25	13.18	2.20
	Org	1.23	1.41	4.35	0.07
Boreal	Conv	11.27	2.98	16.27	7.22
	Org	9.80	2.58	13.67	5.47
Cont	Conv	8.12	1.90	10.61	5.15
	Org	7.42	2.63	11.44	3.23
Lusit	Conv	5.56	1.19	8.56	4.49
	Org	10.11	2.69	14.14	4.90
Med_north	Conv	0.92	0.49	2.11	0.48
	Org	0.36	0.26	0.81	0.04
Med_south	Conv	0.75	1.24	4.09	0.05
	Org	0.45	0.13	0.76	0.31
Nemoral	Conv	5.59	2.79	10.72	0.83
	Org	9.87	4.04	16.46	4.89
Pann	Conv	6.80	1.68	9.60	4.82
	Org	4.83	0.86	6.20	3.81

Table 3.6. Total actinobacteria abundance expressed as sum of actinobacteria PLFAs (nmol g⁻¹) found for the different pedoclimatic regions and management practices. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

3.3.3 Total fungi abundance

Fungi PLFAs results are shown in Table 3.7 as function of pedoclimatic region and management. Comparing all data, Fungi PLFAs data ranged between 0.03 and 7.76 nmol g⁻¹, showing significant differences among regions ($F = 26.271$ $P < 0.001$) and the next sequence: Continental^a \geq Boreal^{ab} \approx Lusitanian^{ab} \geq Nemoral^b \approx Pannonian^b \approx Atlantic Central^b $>$ Atlantic North^c \approx Mediterranean North^c \approx Mediterranean South^c. Overall data did not show significant differences between conventional and organic management systems. Comparing management practices at each region, differences were found for Fungi PLFAs at Atlantic North ($Z = 2.540$, $P < 0.01$), Lusitanian ($Z = 2.357$, $P < 0.05$), Mediterranean North ($Z = 2.248$, $P < 0.05$), Mediterranean South ($Z = -2.202$, $P < 0.05$) and Pannonian ($t = 3.182$, $P < 0.01$). However, these results are not consistent, since in 4 cases conventional show higher values than organic farming practices, but in other one the opposite trend was found.

3.3.4 Arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi abundance

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) abundance, expressed as AMF NLFAs, is shown in Table 3.8 for 9 pedoclimatic regions and management practices (organic and conventional), ranging between 0.18 and 86.91 nmol g⁻¹. The region factor led to significant differences ($F = 25.685$, $P < 0.001$) resulting a sequence as Mediterranean South^a \approx Mediterranean North^a $>$ Atlantic North^b \geq Pannonian^{bc} \geq Nemoral^{bc} \geq Boreal^{bcd} \approx Atlantic Central^{bcd} \approx Continental^{bcd} \geq Lusitanian^d. Overall results did not provide significant differences between management practices for AMF PLFAs. Performing regional analysis, conventional management systems was significantly different from organic at Atlantic North ($t = -2.600$, $P < 0.05$), Continental ($t = -5.285$, $P < 0.001$), Lusitanian ($t = 2.613$, $P < 0.05$), Mediterranean North ($t = -3.294$, $P < 0.01$) and Nemoral ($t = -2.772$, $P < 0.05$). However, these results are not consistent, since in 4 cases conventional show lower values than organic farming practices, but in other one the opposite trend was found.

		MEAN	SD	MAX	MIN
Atl_cent	Conv	1.24	0.45	1.87	0.31
	Org	1.45	0.70	2.71	0.57
Atl_north	Conv	0.41	0.08	0.51	0.26
	Org	0.27	0.36	1.24	0.03
Boreal	Conv	2.46	1.96	7.76	0.95
	Org	2.53	1.84	7.39	1.28
Cont	Conv	3.35	0.92	4.78	2.26
	Org	3.03	1.62	5.64	0.90
Lusit	Conv	2.85	1.04	5.68	1.90
	Org	1.74	1.09	3.84	0.17
Med_north	Conv	0.45	0.45	1.64	0.18
	Org	0.17	0.13	0.38	0.03
Med_south	Conv	0.11	0.03	0.16	0.08
	Org	0.26	0.34	1.21	0.09
Nemoral	Conv	1.28	0.45	2.02	0.82
	Org	1.62	0.50	2.58	0.95
Pann	Conv	1.58	0.29	1.99	1.15
	Org	1.12	0.32	1.72	0.70

Table 3.7. Total fungi abundance expressed as fungi PLFA (nmol g⁻¹) found for the different pedoclimatic regions and management practices. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

TABLE 3.8

		MEAN	SD	MAX	MIN
Atl_cent	Conv	5.29	11.77	42.28	0.42
	Org	2.57	2.47	7.73	0.36
Atl_north	Conv	4.25	2.74	9.03	0.59
	Org	9.19	5.20	16.71	1.30
Boreal	Conv	4.15	2.01	8.60	1.52
	Org	4.21	2.51	7.25	0.22
Cont	Conv	0.72	0.18	1.01	0.41
	Org	4.67	2.36	8.89	1.70
Lusit	Conv	3.42	2.64	8.73	0.41
	Org	1.18	0.66	2.47	0.18
Med_north	Conv	14.94	9.12	29.18	3.40
	Org	41.22	23.23	86.14	15.74
Med_south	Conv	36.37	22.35	86.91	7.78
	Org	30.10	14.36	49.07	0.26
Nemoral	Conv	3.48	1.95	6.31	0.92
	Org	7.49	4.15	14.30	2.41
Pann	Conv	4.99	5.19	16.18	0.40
	Org	6.95	4.48	14.45	1.89

Table 3.8. Arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi (AMF) abundance expressed as AMF NLFA (nmol g^{-1}) found for the different pedoclimatic regions and management practices. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

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4 Nematode diversity

4.1 Introduction

The SoildiverAgro-project decided to focus on a suit of organism groups including nematodes. Nematodes or roundworms are a diverse, highly specialised group of organisms, inhabiting virtually all ecosystems (Hodda et al., 2009). In the soil, they frequently are the most abundant and diverse invertebrates present with species occurring across multiple trophic levels (Yeates et al., 1993). They are more sensitive to external stimuli of mechanical, chemical or physical nature compared to other organisms due to their permeable cuticle and sensory organs (Goodman and Sengupta, 2019); numerous species can withstand anaerobic conditions and desiccation which benefits their survival (McSorley, 2003); their generation time (days to years) is longer than metabolically active microbes (hours to days) making them more stable temporally and not simply fluctuating with nutrient flushes (Nannipieri et al., 1990). Nematodes are easy to extract from the soil using simple extraction procedures and they can be sampled in all seasons (Ritz and Trudgill, 1999). As a consequence, the composition of the nematode community delivers key information on the functioning of the soil (Ferris et al., 2009; Bongers et al., 1999). This implies that any natural or anthropogenic interference will likely be reflected in the nematode community. A recent study on biological indicators useful to monitor soil biodiversity and ecosystem functions conducted by a panel of approximately 50 European soil biology researchers listed nematodes on the top based on an overall ranking score taking the following criteria into account: measurable, availability of cost-effective screening methods, policy-relevance, sensitivity, and fit for use (Griffiths et al., 2016).

Nematodes are microscopically small but constitute a big proportion of the soil fauna. Most individuals are beneficial as they participate in improving soil fertility (Schmidt et al., 2020), soil disease suppression (Wang and McSorley, 2005) and soil structure (Jiang et al., 2018). However, on the contrary to bacteria, fungi and earthworms, nematodes are generally unknown by farmers and the public with a possible exception of certain harmful species. One group in particular differs from other groups due to their specialization in parasitizing plants causing a large reduction on crop quality and yield (Jones et al., 2013). Some species have only one plant family in which they can survive, other species can develop in a broader range of plants. Because of their close relationship with plants more than soil itself, plant-parasitic nematodes are usually not considered to infer functional biodiversity based on nematode-specific indices (Bongers, 1990; Ferris et al., 2001).

While there are many general indices of biological diversity, for example the Shannon (Spellerberg, 2003), Simpson (Simpson, 1949) and Chao1 (Chao, 1984) index, specific indices have been developed for nematodes to infer functional diversity. The difference with biological diversity is that functional diversity studies also consider the interaction of organisms with their environment (Calow, 1987). Hence, functional biodiversity more accurately measures the provision of ecosystem services as the latter are related to the roles organisms play in the soil ecosystem. Yeates et al., (1993) categorized

nematodes, based on their feeding habits into five generally recognized trophic groups: bacterivores, fungivores, predators, omnivores and plant parasites. Bongers (1990) classified free-living nematodes, based on their life-style, along a colonizer-persister (c-p) continuum of 1-5. Nematodes with c-p value equal to 1 are usually small sized, short lived, have high fecundity, a good tolerance to disturbances and predominantly are bacteria- and fungi-feeders whereas those of c-p value 5 have large body size, longer life span, low fecundity, susceptible to disturbance and are predominantly omnivores and predators (Bongers, 1990). Ferris (1993) argued that use of trophic groups alone could often lead to ambiguous results since the trophic groups encompass an enormous diversity of life history and physiological characteristics, and that the c-p classification as suggested by Bongers (1990) assumes a progression of soil conditions from stressed or polluted to pristine while the most abundant nematode taxa under stressed conditions are those in c-p 2, not c-p 1. Therefore, in an attempt to improve the indicator capabilities of nematodes, weights were assigned to indicator nematode guilds representing basal, enriched and structured conditions of the food web. This concept leads to the development of food web indices including enrichment (EI) and structure index (SI). EI is based on the expected responsiveness of the opportunistic guilds (c-p 1 bacterivore nematodes) to organic resources enrichment. Therefore, EI describes whether the soil environment is nutrient enriched (high EI) or depleted (low EI). SI represents an aggregation of functional guilds with c-p values ranging from 3 to 5 and describes whether the soil ecosystem is structured with greater trophic links (high SI) or degraded (low SI) with fewer trophic links (Ferris et al., 2001). Plotting of EI and SI provide a model framework of nematode faunal analysis as an indicator of the likely conditions of the soil food web in a given habitat (see figure 4.1). Further, Ferris et al., (2001) also proposed the channel index (CI), which is a percentage of fungivores among the total fungivores and c-p 1 opportunists bacterivores. CI indicates predominant decomposition channels in the soil food web, a high CI (> 50 %) indicates fungal decomposition channels whereas low CI (< 50 %) suggests bacterial decomposition channels (Ferris et al., 2001).

In recent literature it has been reported that different practices within agricultural management systems, as well as soil characteristics, may play an important role in shaping the biodiversity of nematodes (Quist et al., 2016). This report however, wants to investigate the effect of 2 agricultural systems (system approach), organic and conventional farming, on soil nematode community compositions in European croplands across nine different pedoclimatic regions.

Figure 4.1. Functional guilds of soil nematodes characterized by feeding habit (trophic group) and by life history characteristics expressed along a colonizer-persister (cp) scale (cp scale proposed by Bongers and Bongers, 1998). Bax (bacterivores), Fux (fungivores), Cax (carnivores), Omx (omnivores) (where value of x = 1-5 on the cp scale) represents various functional guilds. Indicator guilds of soil food web condition (basal, structured, enriched) are designated and weightings of the guilds along the structure and enrichment trajectories are provided (figures between brackets), for determination of the Enrichment Index and Structure Index of the food web. From Ferris et al., 2001.

4.2 Material and Methods

4.2.1 Introduction

The characterization of nematode communities, based on morphology and morphometrical measurements using microscopy, requires a high level of expertise and is extremely time-consuming. This is why a traditional morphological analysis of a nematode suspension from a soil sample containing easily a few thousands of individuals, is mostly restricted to 100-200 individuals, what can cause biased results regarding the presence and abundance of different species. Several years ago research was initiated to establish alternative methodologies based on the use of DNA-metabarcoding (or amplicon sequencing, a Next Generation Sequencing method). Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) revolutionized DNA sequencing by allowing massive parallel sequencing with

millions of reactions running in the same experiment. For nematode metabarcoding, the V6-V8 region of the 18S rRNA gene is usually targeted as it has proven to be a good marker with a satisfying taxonomic coverage of nematode genera present in an environmental sample (Bik et al., 2013; Creer et al., 2010; Darby et al., 2013; Porazinska et al., 2009; Waeyenberge et al., 2019). The use of multiplex identifiers for sample-specific labelling of nucleic acids allows the analysis of hundreds of samples in a single instrument run, extending DNA-based species identification from individuals to communities. This high-throughput, sensitive method increases the speed of nematode community characterization and significantly decreases costs associated with the sampling and sequencing of bulk samples.

As part of work package 4, DNA-extraction of nematode communities and the processing of raw sequence data, with special attention to taxon assignment, were optimized. Only the changes in the bio-informatics pipeline were implemented for the analysis of nematode community sequences from samples of work package 3 because, on the contrary to soil samples or nematode suspensions, sequence data can be stored and re-analysed repeatedly, at different moments, with different software packages. Applying the optimized DNA-extraction method on a subset of samples is to be avoided as this will cause variation in the data not related to biological features.

4.2.2 Nematode extraction

Nematode communities were collected from 188 soil samples (up to 100ml) using an automated zonal centrifuge (Hendrickx, 1995). This technique uses a separation liquid ($MgSO_4$) with a certain density to separate the nematodes (and some other organic particles and organisms) from the mineral fraction of the soil during centrifugation. The result is a nematode suspension in 150ml of water with a residual amount of the separation liquid. The nematode suspension is reduced until approximately 40ml after a minimum of 4 hours. During that time nematodes sank to the bottom of the beaker. At this point, the beakers can be stored at 4°C during one week.

4.2.3 Morphological analysis

The nematode suspension or a well-defined fraction is poured into a counting dish and all nematodes are counted using a binocular microscope (Leica M80, 40X) . Additionally, the number of individuals of certain economically important plant-parasitic nematode genera is determined too. After pouring the suspension back into the corresponding beaker, the nematode suspension is further concentrated as explained in "Handbook - protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis" (Calviño et al., 2020).

4.2.4 DNA extraction and library prep.

From each concentrated nematode suspension, DNA is extracted using the DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit (Qiagen) with few modifications. The quality and concentration of the DNA samples were checked with Nanodrop ND-1000 UV-spectrofotometer (ThermoFisher Scientific) and Quantus E6150 fluorometer (Promega) respectively. A library prep is made from each nematode DNA extract by applying a 2-step amplification process. Amplicon libraries with sample-specific indices for approximately 300 DNA-extracts were pooled in equimolar amounts according to the instructions provided by the sequence service (Admera Health Biopharma Services, New Jersey, USA) and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq PE300 platform (2 x 300 bp). A more detailed description of this procedure can be found in "Handbook - protocols for sampling, general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis" (Calviño et al., 2020).

4.2.5 Bio-informatics pipeline for raw sequence data clean-up

After receiving the raw sequence data from the sequence service provider, the data is analysed and quality checked. Poor quality sequences ($70\% \geq Q30$) were removed. Primer sequences were removed from the obtained reads using Trimmomatic v0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014), adapters were removed with cutadapt v3.3 (Martin, 2011), forward and reverse sequences were merged with PEAR v.0.9.11 (Zhang et al., 2014) and the sequences with N's or more than six expected errors were filtered with vsearch v. 2.17.0 (Rognes et al., 2016). DADA2 v1.18 (Callahan et al., 2016) was used to model and correct Illumina-sequenced amplicon errors in the obtained sequences. It subsequently infers exactly the sequences into amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) and resolves differences of as little as one nucleotide. Chimeric sequences were identified and removed using the consensus method implemented in the DADA2 function `removeBimeraDenovo`. The RDP Naive Bayesian Classifier algorithm (Wang et al., 2007), also implemented in the DADA2 package, was used to assign taxonomic units to ASV using an in-house curated custom NCBI reference database.

4.2.6 Nematode community sequence analysis

The R package phyloseq v. 1.36.0 (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) analysis was used to calculate relative abundances for each sequence variant per sample subsequently followed by removing taxa below 0.1% relative abundance summed across all samples in a pedoclimatic region. Alpha diversity indices (Chao 1, Shannon, Simpson) were calculated with phyloseq. Cumulative sum scaling (CSS) normalization of the ASV table implemented in the R package microbiomeSeq v. 0.1, was used for subsequent NMDS ordination and beta diversity analysis based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index with phyloseq. The abundances of taxa were compared with DESeq2 v. 1.32.0 (Love et al., 2014) to

determine key drivers (i.e., taxonomic groups) responsible for any observed differences. For all statistical comparisons, p-values below 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

The homogeneity of variance was tested using Levene's test. When data was normally distributed, the statistical significance of differences between regions and agricultural management systems were estimated using one-way ANOVA. When the data was not normally distributed, the Kruskal–Wallis or Mann-Whitney U test was used for more than 2 or 2 independent groups respectively (Statistica v 14.0.0.15, Tibco). Permanova was applied to test the effect of region, agricultural management system (organic or conventional) and the interaction between them on the nematode ASV composition.

Nematode-specific ecological indices (Enrichment Index, Structural index, Channel Index) based on nematode community data can be calculated automatically by importing a list of nematode genera into the online freely accessible program NINJA <https://sieriebriennikov.shinyapps.io/ninja/>. NINJA stands for Nematode INDicator Joint Analysis (Sieriebriennikov et al., 2014). The Enrichment Index and Structural index are further used to plot a Food Web Analysis (Figure 4.1) (Ferris et al., 2001).

It has been reported that the frequencies of sequence reads assigned to certain nematode taxa don't correlate with the absolute numbers of individuals of the concerned taxa present in a soil sample (Creer et al., 2010). Various reasons can be recited but this phenomenon cannot yet be solved. As a result, the number of individuals belonging to certain nematode genera are overrated, while others are underrated following DNA-metabarcoding (Bik et al., 2013). During WP4, tests are conducted to improve quantification using DNA-metabarcoding. In the meantime it is decided to only use sequence data not to assess biodiversity *per se* due to the incorrectness of relative proportions between certain nematode genera but to compare WP3 data with each other: does sample A has a better (functional) biodiversity compared to sample B.

4.3 Results and discussion

4.3.1 Absolute number of nematodes and some economically important plant-parasitic nematode taxa

The absolute number of nematode individuals and of certain economically important plant-parasitic nematode genera can be found in Annex (Table A4.1). Boxplots of the number of nematodes show a large variation within and between the regions (Figure 4.2). None of the regions are significantly different from all other regions (Kruskal-Wallis). Also no significant difference could be found between the agricultural systems means (conventional vs. organic) as determined by one-way ANOVA (Figure 4.3). When we consider the regions separately, than again no significant difference

could be found between the agricultural systems with exception of the Pannonian and Boreal region ($p < 0,05$).

Figure 4.2. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes for each region. Significant differences were tested with Kruskal-Wallis ($H(8,188) = 91,0585$; $\chi^2 = 62,28348$, $p = 0,0000$). No region was significant different from all other regions. The specific regions are indicated by colour; Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Almost all sampled fields contain economically important plant-parasitic nematodes (Table A4.1). The genus *Pratylenchus* is distributed worldwide (Castillo and Vovlas, 2007). This is reflected in the fact that *Pratylenchus* species were found in more than 96% of the sampled fields. In most regions, some fields are heavily infected with more than 1000 individuals per 100cc of soil. Infection is followed by a reduction in root growth, and is visible by the formation of lesions, necrotic areas, browning and cell death. Moreover, *Pratylenchus* species are migratory endoparasites and this feeding behavior causes a lot of opportunities for a secondary attack by soil fungi or bacteria like *Erwinia*, *Rhizoctonia*, *Verticillium* and *Fusarium*, causing root rotting and other symptoms (Castillo and Vovlas, 2007). Probably due to these secondary infestations, *Pratylenchus* spp. are often underestimated pests causing economic losses for many crops (Jones et al., 2013).

Another widely-spread nematode genus is *Paratylenchus*. *Paratylenchus* is a migratory ectoparasite and even high numbers of individuals appear to cause little damage with an exception to a few crops like carrot, cabbages and celeriac (Ingham et al., 1996). Although, it should be noted that this genus

is not very well studied yet. This genus could be found in 66% of the sampled fields. The number of individuals determined are relatively low (<200 individuals per 100cc of soil) with few exceptions.

Figure 4.3. Boxplots of the absolute number of nematodes for each agricultural system (conv = conventional, org = organic). Significant differences were tested with one-way ANOVA ($p > 0,05$). No significant difference could be found between both systems.

The most economically important nematodes, the root-knot (*Meloidogyne* sp.) and cyst nematodes (*Globodera* and *Heterodera* sp.), are obligate plant parasites (sedentary endoparasitic). They induce complex feeding structures in the roots of their hosts which supply the nematode with a rich and long-lasting food source (Jones et al., 2013). The damage they cause are significant on both quality and yield, therefore species of both genera are listed as quarantine species in Europe (<https://www.eppo.int/index>). Root-knot nematodes parasitize almost every species of vascular plant. Their name comes from the galls (root-knots) they induce on the roots of their host plant (Perry et al., 2009). None of the regions were completely free of a root-knot nematode infestation (33% of the fields infested) but in the following regions more regularly root-knot nematode species could be found: Atlantic Central, Atlantic North and all 3 regions in Spain. The most damaging cyst-forming nematode species include soybean cyst nematodes (*Heterodera glycines*), potato cyst nematodes (*Globodera pallida* and *G. rostochiensis*) and cereal cyst nematodes (including *Heterodera avenae* and *H. filipjevi*) (Jones et al., 2013). Particular problems are caused by the ability of cyst nematodes to survive for prolonged periods in the soil in the absence of a host, making eradication, once established, almost impossible (Grainger, 1964). In many fields (44%) of almost all regions, high to low number of individuals could be found. Only in the Boreal and Atlantic North regions just a couple of fields (1 and 3 respectively) were infested.

From the genus *Ditylenchus* only a few parasitize higher plants. They have a migratory endoparasitic lifestyle (Duncan and Moens, 2006). For Europe, *D. destructor*, a pest of potato tubers, and *D. dipsaci*, a pest for a wide host range, are economically important. However, the best known species is *D. dipsaci*, probably because of its amazing ability to survive severe desiccation for more than 20 years (Perry and Moens, 2011) and because it is on the list of quarantine organisms of many countries. *Ditylenchus* was found in 40% of the fields sampled but in low numbers (max. 28 individuals per 100cc of soil).

The genus *Rotylenchus* could be detected in 36% of the fields sampled but only in the Atlantic Central, Atlantic North, Boreal and Nemoral regions it seems to be well-spread. *Rotylenchus* species can be facultative endoparasitic but seem not to be a big economic problem for arable farming, only it is known to be real damaging for carrot. However, still a lot of information on damage thresholds and multiplication rates is missing (Castillo and Vovlas, 2005).

In only 17% of the fields sampled, individuals belonging to the genera *Xiphinema* and *Longidorus* could be detected. In all soil samples less than 25 individuals per 100cc were counted. Relatively little biological and ecological work has been done on these ectoparasitic genera most probably because some species are difficult to maintain in greenhouse cultures, others have a very long life-cycle. The nematodes themselves are seldom of major importance as they rarely attain high population levels when soil is frequently disturbed. However, some species are vectors of plant viruses (nepoviruses) and the damage caused by the viruses may be independent of the abundance of nematodes (Brown et al., 1995).

Also species belonging to the family of Trichodoridae are capable of transmitting viruses (tobraviruses) (Brown et al., 1995). On the contrary to the genera *Xiphinema* and *Longidorus*, *Prartrichodorus* and *Trichodorus* species are known to cause by themselves important damage to arable crops like sugar beet, onion, potato, peas, bean and carrot (Winfield and Cooke, 1975). Individuals belonging to the family of Trichodoridae could only be determined in 16% of the investigated fields. This group seems not to be well-spread in arable fields of Europe as only in 2 regions, Atlantic Central and North, it was regularly found.

4.3.2 Nematode community sequence data

The number of read clusters for all 188 samples together was 7 664 469. After quality filtering, merging forward and reverse reads, and removal of chimeric sequences, 3 522 936 or 45.96% (mean 18 739) were used for further analysis. One sample (CONO1A) contains only 30 sequences and thus has to be used with caution as rarefaction shows that for this sample the biodiversity surely was not fully covered (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4. Rarefaction plots of all investigated samples per region. All samples show a plateau-phase suggesting that all samples have been sufficiently sequenced to represent its biodiversity with exception of CONO1A (Continental region).

Two consecutive filtering steps further reduced the number of sequences. Firstly, all ASV's that could not be assigned taxonomically to a lower taxonomic level than a nematode class, based on our in house curated nematode sequence database, were removed. This caused a reduction of the number of sequence reads till 2 876 042 (81,64%) . Blasting of a selection of the removed sequences revealed that these sequences are not from nematodes but from Arthropoda, Annelida, Tardigrada, Rotifera, Amoebzoa, Endomyxa etc. Secondly, all ASV's with an abundance of less than 0,1% compared to the mean number of sequence reads of all samples per region, were removed as well, leading to a remainder of 2 527 629 sequence reads (87,89%) comprising 482 ASV's for all regions together. Finally, sequences with the same taxonomic assignment at genus level were summed. The final tables comprises 109 nematode taxa (genus level) for all samples together ready for downstream analyses.

4.3.3 Alpha-diversity

The alpha-diversity results of the regions are not completely consistent between the different indices (Observed, Chao1, Shannon and Simpson). Lusitanian region shows a reduced biodiversity for observed and Chao 1, but for Shannon and Simpson, this region is accompanied by Mediterranean South. On the opposite, Atlantic North and Pannonian always display an increased alpha-diversity, while for Shannon and Simpson, the Pannonian region is accompanied by Nemoral region (Figure 4.5). The differences between the regions potentially can be explained by climatological, soil physical and chemical differences (van den Hoogen et al., 2019) although it still needs to be investigated which parameters have the highest impact (see deliverable D3.4). Statistically there are no significant differences in alpha-diversity when considering all regions together as calculated by Kruskal-Wallis ($p > 0.05$). The same can be concluded when the systems are compared for all regions together as inferred by one-way ANOVA or Mann-Whitney ($p > 0.05$) (Figure 4.6). Only when the regions were analysed separately, a significant difference between the systems could be noticed in exceptional cases for one of the alpha diversity indices, for example Observed and Chao 1 in Atlantic North and Continental regions, and Shannon and Simpson in Mediterranean South region ($p < 0.05$). So we can conclude that the alpha-biodiversity was not altered by the organic agricultural system compared to conventional farming.

Figure 4.5. Box plots of the alpha-diversity distribution in all regions, based on the number of ASV's. Kruskal-Wallis ($p > 0.05$) did not observe significant differences. Each colour corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region; All_cent = Atlantic Central, All_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure 4.6. Box plots of the alpha-diversity distribution for each agricultural systems of all regions together based on the number of ASV's. One-way ANOVA for Shannon and Simpson and Mann-Whitney for Observed and Chao 1 did not display significant differences ($p > 0,05$), conv = conventional and org = organic farming system.

4.3.4 Beta-diversity

Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) reveals that there is no separate grouping of the agricultural systems based on the nematode communities of all regions together (Figure 4.7). The impact of the agricultural systems on the nematode community composition was statistically calculated. Permanova analysis (Table 4.1) concluded that the pedoclimatic regions can explain 34 % of the observed variance in the nematode community composition while the agricultural management systems only had a minor (<10%) impact. It is clear that the diversity is directed more by the region with its specific conditions concerning climate and soil characteristics than by the agricultural system. Indeed, permanova shows an increasing value to explain variance in nematode community composition explained by the systems used when considering the regions separately. This indicates that a more profound investigation considering different aspects of the agricultural management systems and/or chemical and physical spoil properties per region is needed to explain differences in biodiversity.

Figure 4.7. NMDS plots of all samples. Different colours are used to indicate the regions (Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian), a different symbol is used for the systems (circles are conventional (conv), triangles organic (org) farming systems). There is no grouping of the systems, grouping is more obvious when considering the regions.

4.3.5 Indicator nematode taxa for both agricultural management systems per region

A log₂FoldChange analysis was performed to identify taxa that had a differential abundance between the two agricultural management systems (Figure 4.8). To avoid differences based on climatological factors, the log₂FoldChange was only calculated within the regions. Pannonian showed most changes with 18 taxa showing a differential abundance. Taxa from different levels in the Food Web Chain had a positive or negative log₂FoldChange and thus had a significant higher or lower abundance in organic farming respectively. Those taxa with a higher abundance are predators (*Mononchus*, *Seinura*, *Oxydirus*), a fungivore (*Aphelenchoides*), herbivores (*Neopsilenchus*, *Boleodorus*, *Coslenchus*), and bacterivores (*Tylocephalus*, *Panagrolaimus*, *Acrobeloides*). Taxa that have a lower abundance are herbivores (*Pratylenchus*, *Geocenamus*, *Paratylenchus*), a fungivore (*Hexatylus*), depending on the species fungivore or herbivore (*Ditylenchus*), bacterivores (*Diploscapter*, *Prismatolaimus*) and an entomopathogenic nematode taxon (*Steinernema*).

TABLE 4.1

SOURCE	F	R2	P
ALL REGIONS			
Management	2.1639	0.00737	0.001
Region	12.4801	0.34	0.001
Region & Management	2.7059	0.07372	0.001
Residuals		0.57892	
Different REGIONS			
Management Atl_cent	3.2536	0.12393	0.001
Management Atl_north	3.1541	0.1491	0.001
Management Boreal	---	---	> 0,05
Management Cont	3.9282	0.17914	0.001
Management Lusit	2.9555	0.12337	0.001
Management Med_north	---	---	>0,05
Management Med_south	5.1528	0.22256	0.001
Management Nemoral	1.6256	0.08283	0.023
Management Pann	1.9206	0.09641	0.017

Table 4.2. PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of region, management (organic or conventional management) and the interaction between them on the nematode ASV composition. Differences are considered significant if $p \leq 0.05$. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

The Boreal region has 12 taxa with a significant differential abundance. Some bacterivore (*Panagrolaimus*, *Plectus*, *Rhabditis*, *Alaimus*), a herbivore (*Litylenchus*), a fungivore (*Diphtherophora*) and a predator (*Oxydirus*) show a significant higher abundance in the organic systems. *Aphelenchoides* and *Filenchus*, both fungivore taxa, showed both a taxon that had a higher and lower significant abundance. The fungivore genus *Bursaphelenchus*, the herbivore genus *Pratylenchus* and the herbivore or fungivore genus *Ditylenchus* had a significant lower abundance in the organic system in comparison with the conventional farming system.

In the Mediterranean South region 10 taxa have a significant differential abundance. *Paratylenchus*, *Globodera*, *Heterodera* (herbivores), *Aphelenchus* (fungivore), *Ditylenchus* (herbivore or fungivore) and *Panagrolaimus* (bacterivore) have a significant higher abundance in the organic systems. *Acrobeloides*, a bacterivore, have both a higher and lower significant abundance. The fungivore genus *Aphelenchoides*, the herbivore genera *Pratylenchus* and *Geocenamus* have a significant lower abundance in comparison with the conventional farming system.

Figure 4.8. log₂FoldChange ASVs representation at genus level for management type, performed using DeSeq2. Each dot represents a single ASV, only those taxa showing significant differences in abundance between the conventional and organic framing are shown. Negative values indicate the log₂ fold change for taxa underrepresented in an organic system. Positive values indicate the log₂ fold change for taxa overrepresented in organic system. Different colours are used to differentiate nematode taxa on family level.

The Continental region has seven taxa with a significant differential abundance. The bacterivore genus *Panagrolaimus* had a significant higher abundance. Some fungivore genera (*Aphelenchoides*, *Filenchus* and *Hexatylylus*), a herbivore (*Coslenchus*), a bacterivore (*Acrobeloides*) and a herbivore/fungivore (*Ditylenchus*) taxon had a significant lower abundance in the organic systems.

In the Atlantic North region six nematode genera show a significant differential abundance of which the herbivore taxa (*Pratylenchus*, *Paratylenchus*, *Trichodorus*) and a fungivore taxon (*Aphelenchoides*) have a higher abundance, the bacterivore taxa (*Acrobeloides*, *Panagrolaimus*) a lower abundance in the organic systems.

The Atlantic Central region contains five nematode genera that had a significant differential abundance. Some herbivores (*Heterodera* and *Pratylenchus*) have a significant higher abundance,

Protorhabditis, *Panagrolaimus* (both bacterivores) and an omnivore (*Pristionchus*) have a significant lower abundance in the organic systems.

In the Lusitanian region, the bacterivore genera *Protorhabditis* and *Acrobeloides* had a significant lower abundance in the organic systems compared to the conventional farming systems.

For the Mediterranean North and Nemoral regions there was only a significant differential abundance observed for the herbivore or fungivore genus *Ditylenchus* with a significant lower abundance in the organic systems.

Nematode taxa showing a significant differential abundance in organic farming for all regions could not be found. However, some taxa showed a significantly increased or reduced abundance in 5 or 6 out of 9 regions and thus have a potential to become a common indicator for organic systems, for example *Acrobeloides*, *Aphelenchoides*, *Ditylenchus*, *Panagrolaimus* and *Pratylenchus*. Others were only significantly different in abundance in 1 or 2 regions and thus are potential indicators on a regional level. Much, of course, depends on the fact whether those nematode taxa are wide-spread or not. Another factor for all nematodes is their life-style. Nematodes with a lower reproductive rate (almost) cannot survive regularly disturbed habitats like agricultural fields and therefore have a lower possibility to become an indicator. Unfortunately, the latter often are predators or omnivores and thus belong to a higher trophic level. Such taxa are important to assess the food web complexity. Only in the *Pannonian* region several nematode taxa, showing a significantly increased abundance, are predators, indicative for an increased food web complexity in the organic farming systems compared to the conventional farming systems.

In some regions, plant-parasitic nematode species are considered as indicator taxa. As mentioned before, several such nematode taxa are closely related and highly depending on the host plant(s), the crop(s) – not *Pratylenchus*, as it has a broad host range - and therefore should be considered as an indicator concerning agricultural management systems with caution.

4.3.6 Nematode functional biodiversity

Functional biodiversity was investigated because it has been determined that relations between soil biodiversity and ecosystem functions tend to depend more on structural and functional diversity than on species richness or taxonomic parameters per se (Nielsen et al., 2010). To be able to use nematode communities for functional biodiversity assessments, nematode taxa were assigned to nematode guilds representing basal, enriched and structured conditions of the food web. However, not all nematode taxa could be assigned to a functional guild due to lack of knowledge on the biology of the nematode taxon in question. An average of 69% of the nematode taxa (ASV's) present in all investigated samples could be retained for functional diversity assessment.

The Enrichment and Structural Index were calculated and used to plot a Food Web Analysis (Figure 4.9). On this plot we can see that most of the data points are positioned on the upper half, without

an obvious difference between the two systems (conventional and organic). This is quite normal for agricultural fields as farmers put nutrients on their fields for the crops to grow. The latter causes a shift in the nematode composition leading to an elevated Enrichment Index. Few data points (both agricultural management systems of the Mediterranean North and South regions, as well as the organic systems of the Boreal region) are positioned on the lower part and point towards a nutrient deficiency. On the other hand, most of the data points are positioned on the left side. This is also normal for agricultural fields because such fields are disturbed on many occasions throughout each cropping season (adding fertilizers, soil tillage, planting and harvest operations etc.) and this causes a reduction in the biodiversity and food web complexity (reduced Structural Index). Only few data points (both conventional and organic farming systems) are more positioned on the right and point towards a recovering nematode community. However, it is clear that all nematode community compositions can still improve.

Figure 4.9. Plot of the Food Web Analysis based on the mean Structural Index and Enrichment Index values per region and system. The specific regions are indicated by colour; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian. Agricultural management system is indicated by shape with circles being conventional (conv) and triangles being organic (org) farming systems.

4.4 References

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5 Earthworm diversity

5.1 Introduction

Earthworms are characterized as key members of the soil macrofauna with a broad range of functional roles. According to Turbé et al., (2010) they are (i) chemical engineers by decaying plant residues and controlling nutrient cycles; (ii) biological regulators by grazing on soil microorganisms and thus shaping soil biota communities in space and time; (iii) ecosystem engineers by modifying the soil structure via producing soil aggregates and pore networks which provide habitats for smaller soil organisms and improve the soil water balance and soil aeration. Depending on their morphological characteristics and burrowing behaviour three ecological groups are distinguished (*sensu* Bouché, 1977): (i) epigeic (litter dwellers on and near the soil surface, small size and heavily pigmented); (ii) epiendogeic (species with intermediate characteristics between epigeic and endogeic) (iii) endogeic (mineral-soil burrowers, medium size and lightly pigmented or unpigmented); (iv) anecic (vertical burrowers, large size and pigmented in the front third of the body). In relation to their feeding behaviour, epigeics and anecics are considered as primary decomposers, which feed on energy-rich organic material, whereas endogeics are secondary decomposers feeding on energy-poor organic material, which is already decayed to an advanced stage. Epiendogeics are feeding on more nutritious food and are therefore intermediate between primary and secondary decomposers. This rough ecological and functional classification of earthworms exemplifies their manifold relevance in the soil system.

Earthworms show low tolerance to alterations in their soil physical and chemical environment and to reduced availability of food sources. For these reasons earthworms are sensitive to external inputs as applied in agricultural systems. Frequency and intensity of agricultural management (e.g. tillage), quality of chemical inputs (agrochemicals), type of crop and the number of different crops in rotation are examples of the main factors affecting earthworm species diversity and abundance (see e.g. Whalen and Sampedro, 2010; Bai et al., 2018). These factors have long-lasting impacts on earthworm communities with legacy effects from previous crops (e.g. remaining residues) and management (Lago et al., 2020). Contrary to natural systems, arable systems typically persist in an early stage of succession due to the seasonal sequence of seeding, cultivation and harvest which often impedes the development of species rich earthworm communities.

In addition, climatic conditions are influential factors determining earthworm community structure. Recent data compilations of earthworm surveys have revealed general geographical patterns in species distributions within regions on the European scale (Rutgers et al., 2016) and demonstrated that precipitation strongly affects species richness, abundance and biomass of earthworms on the global scale (Phillips et al., 2019).

To date, a European wide earthworm survey using standardised methods with specific focus on how contrasting agricultural systems affect earthworm community structure across climatic regions has not been produced. Therefore, in this study, our aim was to assess the impacts of conventional and organic farming on earthworm communities from nine pedoclimatic regions of Europe to elucidate how the local soil and environmental conditions as well as agricultural management shape their communities.

5.2 Material and Methods

At each of the nine pedoclimatic regions, 10 fields of conventional and organic management practices, which were grown with wheat, were selected for earthworm sampling as for the other soil biota groups (see chapters 1 to 4). When feasible, two fields from an organic and a conventional farm situated at the same locality were sampled. Most regions were sampled between August and November 2019 depending on weather conditions. However, the two Mediterranean regions were sampled half a year later and the Pannonian region one year later to avoid extreme drought conditions and high temperatures, which characterized many parts of Europe in 2019.

Earthworms were sampled in each field at a representative area from three quadrats by a combined method of hand-sorting and chemical expelling by the active agent in mustard, allyl isothiocyanate (AITC; mustard oil) as described in ISO 23611-1:2018. The sampling area of each plot was 50 cm x 50 cm with exception of the Boreal and Mediterranean region, where an area of 25 cm x 25 cm was sampled due to local soil conditions, which makes the hand-sorting of soil arduous. The sampling depth was 25 cm. A detailed description of the sampling procedures is given in deliverable D3.1 Handbook of Methods (June 2020) (chapter 1.3, pages 18-23) under the URL: <http://soildiveragro.eu/data/D3.1.pdf>

Earthworm metrics obtained were referred to 1 square meter for total earthworm abundance as well as for total biomass (g m^{-2}). The number of species in a sample was used as such for obtaining the mean species number in a field. The different type of data was defined as follows:

- Total abundance: all individuals incl. fragments with intact anterior end ("head") that can be unequivocally counted. This was done to avoid overestimation of population numbers.
- Total biomass: all individuals and fragments (anterior and posterior ends and any middle parts)
- Identified species: those individuals and fragments with intact anterior end ("head") and clitellum/tubercula pubertatis that allowed taxonomical identification.
- Unidentified individuals: only fragments with intact anterior end ("head") when species identification was not possible.

Adult and sub-adult earthworms (tubercula pubertatis present, but clitellum absent or not fully developed) were identified to species level by using a stereo microscope (magnitude: 10x to 50x) and specialized taxonomic identification keys. Here, data on species level are the sum of adults and sub-adults. Adults and sub-adults but also juveniles (when possible) were assigned to their ecological groups (epigeic, epindogeic, endogeic, anecic) according to their dorsal pigmentation. A detailed description of separating developmental stages, assigning individuals to ecological groups and taxonomical identification is given in deliverable D3.1 Handbook of Methods (June 2020) (chapter 4.1, pages 96-99) under the URL: <http://soildiveragro.eu/data/D3.1.pdf>

Earthworm data was analyzed with generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) (Bolker et al., 2009; SAS® GLIMMIX procedure) with pedoclimatic region and management system (conventional vs. organic) as fixed effects and study locality as a random effect. The response variables were earthworm total abundance, total biomass and earthworm species number. Regions and management were compared with Tukey-Kramer multiple comparisons (Day and Quinn, 1989).

Boxplots were used to illustrate the variation in the total abundance and biomass and species richness of earthworms between the regions and between the managements within regions. Figures were made with 'ggplot2' of R package (Wickham, 2016).

5.3 Results and discussion

5.3.1 General effects of pedoclimatic region and agricultural management

The results of the statistical analyses clearly show that pedoclimatic region had a significant effect on the three investigated variables (Table 5.1). Accordingly, the highest earthworm abundances and biomass were recorded in the Boreal region whereas the lowest values were measured in the Mediterranean regions (Figures. 5.1, 5.3). Agricultural management did not have a significant effect on earthworm community metrics (Table 5.1). In total, nineteen different species were identified from all investigated regions. The highest species richness on average was found in Atlantic Central (11 species), Lusitanian (9 species) and Pannonian (9 species) regions (Table 5.2).

TABLE 5.1

EFFECT	ABUNDANCE		BIOMASS		NUMBER OF SPECIES	
	F	P-value	F	P-value	F	P-value
Region	13.75	< 0.0001	6.52	<0.0001	29.04	<0.0001
Management	0.58	0.449	0.00	0.988	1.20	0.276
Region & Management	0.77	0.628	0.90	0.523	1.08	0.382

Table 5.1 Results of generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) analyses for earthworm total abundance, total biomass and number of species covering 9 pedoclimatic regions in Europe. Significant results are given in bold.

5.3.2 Total earthworm abundance

The results for total earthworm abundances (Fig. 5.1) evidenced the existence of high variability across European pedoclimatic regions, although the mean densities typically ranged between 0 and 150 individuals per m² in agreement with previous global estimates (Phillips et al., 2019). In addition, a clear latitudinal/climatic gradient was observed, with colder and wet climates rendering the highest population densities and the hot and dry Continental and Mediterranean regions sustaining small population sizes. Previous European surveys showed an inverse latitudinal gradient in earthworm abundance (Rutgers et al., 2016) that was attributed to historical factors (Mathieu and Davies, 2014) and contradicts our results. However, a likely additional explanation is the heterogeneous sampling schedule between regions due to climatic constraints in the year of sampling (see chapter 5.2). Importantly, precipitation and temperature regimes have been highlighted as an important regulating factor of earthworm population sizes (Walsh and Johnson-Maynard, 2016; Phillips et al., 2019) which also explains the low abundances recorded under Mediterranean and Continental regions in line with previous estimates (Rutgers et al., 2016; Castro et al., 2019).

Agricultural management (conventional vs. organic) did not significantly affect the abundance of earthworms at each of the pedoclimatic regions (Table 5.1; Figure 5.2). Contrary to our expectations intensive management (conventional) did not always result in lower earthworm densities, with the majority of the regions exhibiting positive responses (Atlantic North, Boreal, Continental, Nemoral and Pannonian) or no differences between agricultural systems (Atlantic Central and Mediterranean climates; Figure 5.2). Previous studies have linked intensive agricultural practices to lower earthworm densities as a result of tillage injuring earthworms and exposing them to predators (Briones and Schmidt, 2017). Especially in organic farming, ploughing is necessary in most cases to control weeds. In conventional management systems, farmers have often switched to less intensive reduced tillage practices with much less harmful consequences for earthworms and the soil biodiversity pool in general (van Capelle et al., 2012). In our survey, 30% of the fields under conventional farming are managed by reduced tillage (mainly in Atlantic North, Boreal, Continental and Nemoral regions),

whereas this is true for only 15% of the fields under organic farming (mainly in Atlantic Central, Lusitanian and Pannonian regions). A positive response to organic management was only observed at the Lusitanian region. This could be the result of local differences in soil properties (e.g. high organic matter content), but more likely climatic conditions exerting a stronger influence than management.

Figure 5.1 Earthworm total abundance in the nine pedoclimatic regions. Boxplots are based on the raw data. Tukey-Kramer multiple comparisons were done for region means predicted by GLMM. Regions marked with same letters are not statistically significantly different ($P > 0.05$); atl_cent = Atlantic Central; atl_north = Atlantic North; boreal = Boreal; cont = Continental; lusit = Lusitanian; med_north = Mediterranean North; med_south = Mediterranean South; nemoral = Nemoral; pann = Pannonian.

5.3.3 Total earthworm biomass

Regional patterns in total earthworm biomass mimicked the results for total abundance (Table 5.1; Figure 5.3) and the recorded values were in agreement with global estimates (i.e. ranging between 1 g and 150 g per m²; Phillips et al., 2019). As with the population numbers, there was a positive relationship between latitude and earthworm biomass, with the highest total biomass being recorded in the Boreal region followed by Atlantic North and Nemoral areas. Precipitation and habitat cover have been identified as the main factors affecting the biomass of earthworm communities, with temperature playing a smaller role (Phillips et al., 2019).

The effect of agricultural management on total earthworm biomass within each pedoclimatic region showed more variable results than abundance values, with the majority of the treatment comparisons not showing an obvious effect. The only exception were the Atlantic North, Continental

and Nemoral regions where the conventional treatment favoured higher biomass of earthworms and those of the Lusitanian region where organic systems resulted in greater earthworm biomass (Figure 5.4). This could be an indication of agricultural practices having a modulating effect on earthworm life cycles (Castro et al., 2019).

Figure 5.2 Earthworm total abundance in conventional (red) and organic (blue) management in the nine pedoclimatic regions. Boxplots are based on the raw data. There were no statistically significant differences between the two managements. Notice the unequal y-axis scales; atl_cent = Atlantic Central; atl_north = Atlantic North; boreal = Boreal; cont = Continental; lusit = Lusitanian; med_north = Mediterranean North; med_south = Mediterranean South; nemoral = Nemoral; pann = Pannonian.

5.3.4 Earthworm species richness

Altogether nineteen earthworm species were found in the nine pedoclimatic study regions of the survey (Table 5.2). Their distribution among the ecological groups (*sensu* Bouché, 1977) as follows: 3 species are assigned to epigeics, 2 species to epiendogeics, 10 species to endogeics and 4 species to anecic species (Table 5.2). The three most commonly found species were endogeic earthworms: *Aporrectodea rosea* was present in all regions, *Allolobophora chlorotica* in seven and *Aporrectodea caliginosa* in six regions. Of the deep burrowing, anecic species *Aporrectodea longa* and *Lumbricus terrestris* were both present in five regions. *Lumbricus rubellus* was the most commonly found epigeic litter dwelling species in five regions. Eight of the species were present only in one region. Their restricted ranges corresponded relatively well with the known European distribution patterns, as compared with GBIF-records (<https://www.gbif.org/>).

Figure 5.3 Earthworm total biomass in the nine pedoclimatic regions. Boxplots are based on the raw data. Tukey-Kramer multiple comparisons were done for region means predicted by GLMM. Regions marked with same letters are not statistically significantly different ($P > 0.05$); atl_cent = Atlantic Central; atl_north = Atlantic North; boreal = Boreal; cont = Continental; lusit = Lusitanian; med_north = Mediterranean North; med_south = Mediterranean South; nemoral = Nemoral; pann = Pannonian.

Figure 5.4 Earthworm total biomass in conventional (red) and organic (blue) management in the nine pedoclimatic regions. Boxplots are based on the raw data. There were no statistically significant differences between the two managements. Notice the unequal y-axis scales; atl_cent = Atlantic Central; atl_north = Atlantic North; boreal = Boreal; cont = Continental; lusit = Lusitanian; med_north = Mediterranean North; med_south = Mediterranean South; nemoral = Nemoral; pann = Pannonian.

On average, the number of earthworm species recorded across the nine pedoclimatic regions ranged between 1 and 3 in any given site, which is also in line for previous estimates at European (Rutgers et al., 2016) and global scales (Phillips et al., 2019). Latitude has been found to be inversely correlated to gradients of earthworm diversity (Lavelle, 1983), although the opposite pattern has also been observed (Phillips et al., 2019). Our results did not show an obvious latitudinal trend, and the highest species richness was observed in the Atlantic North and central areas and in the Nemoral region (Figure 5.5). It has been suggested that the number of different species recorded across European countries is unrelated to their abundance (Rutgers et al., 2016) but to local heterogeneity of soil conditions and the presence of unique species with low abundances (e.g. endemics like *Satchellius madeirensis* in the Lusitanian region; see also Table 5.2).

Figure 5.5 Number of earthworm species in the nine pedoclimatic regions. Boxplots are based on the raw data. Tukey-Kramer multiple comparisons were done for region means predicted by GLMM. Regions marked with same letters are not statistically significantly different ($P > 0.05$); atl_cent = Atlantic Central; atl_north = Atlantic North; boreal = Boreal; cont = Continental; lusit = Lusitanian; med_north = Mediterranean North; med_south = Mediterranean South; nemoral = Nemoral; pann = Pannonian.

Agricultural management did not exert a significant effect on earthworm species number (Table 5.1; Figure 5.6). Nevertheless, certain species, in particular large anecics, are more sensitive than others to agricultural practices (Briones and Schmidt, 2017). Consequently, although climate variables are important factors affecting earthworm species richness, local agricultural practices can also alter their community composition. For example, the level and type of fertilisation and the implementation of irrigation systems in dry areas could override the natural structure of the earthworm communities (Castro et al., 2019).

Figure 5.6 Number of earthworm species in conventional (red) and organic (blue) management in the nine pedoclimatic regions. Boxplots are based on the raw data. There were no statistically significant differences between the two managements. Notice the unequal y-axis scales; atl_cent = Atlantic Central; atl_north = Atlantic North; boreal = Boreal; cont = Continental; lusit = Lusitanian; med_north = Mediterranean North; med_south = Mediterranean South; nemoral = Nemoral; pann = Pannonian.

The greater dominance of endogeics is coincidental with previous studies indicating that those species that make frequent incursions to the soil surface to feed (epigeics and anecics) are more prone to be exposed to the harmful effects of agricultural practices (Briones and Schmidt, 2017). In particular, *A. caliginosa* is a widespread species and found to be dominant in European soils (Rutgers et al., 2016), but also other small endogeics such as *A. rosea* and *A. chlorotica* are commonly found in cultivated soils (Briones and Schmidt, 2017).

5.3.5 Conclusions

Organic farming has several features which are potentially beneficial for earthworms including application of organic fertilizers, leys in rotation, cultivation of legumes and no usage of synthetic pesticides. Therefore often but not always comparisons with conventional farming report higher species richness and higher abundances as well as biomass of earthworms in organic farming (Bengtsson et al., 2005; Christel et al., 2021). Our finding of no such effects of organic farming on any of the community metrics is therefore unexpected. Earthworm abundance and community composition in a given field is, however, affected by a multitude of factors such as variation in soil texture, density, moisture and chemical properties (Lee, 1985; Curry, 2004). In a survey type of investigation such as ours, these factors constitute notable sources of uncontrolled natural variation in the data and complicate the estimation of management effects. Further, management in organic farming might not always be more beneficial for earthworms, the necessity to use inversion tillage for weed control being a prime example. Under conventional management practices more and more

TABLE 5.2

SPECIES	ECO-LOGICAL GROUP	REGION								
		Atl_cent	Atl_north	Boreal	Cont	Lusit	Med_north	Med_south	Nemoral	Pann
<i>Eisenia fetida</i>	epigeic	●								●
<i>Lumbricus castaneus</i>	epigeic	●		●					●	
<i>Lumbricus rubellus</i>	epigeic	●	●	●		●			●	
<i>Octolasion tyrtaeum</i>	epi-endogeic			●						
<i>Satchellius madeirensis</i>	epi-endogeic					●				
<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>	endogeic	●	●	●	●				●	●
<i>Allolobophora chlorotica</i>	endogeic	●	●	●	●	●			●	●
<i>Aporrectodea georgii</i>	endogeic									●
<i>Aporrectodea limicola</i>	endogeic	●								
<i>Aporrectodea rosea</i>	endogeic	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
<i>Microscolex dubius</i>	endogeic						●			
<i>Microscolex phosphoreus</i>	endogeic					●				
<i>Octolasion cyaneum</i>	endogeic	●			●	●			●	
<i>Octolasion lacteum</i>	endogeic	●								●
<i>Proctodrilus antipai</i>	endogeic									●
<i>Aporrectodea longa</i>	anecic	●	●			●			●	●
<i>Aporrectodea trapezoides</i>	anecic					●		●		●
<i>Lumbricus friendi</i>	anecic					●				
<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i>	anecic	●	●	●	●				●	

Table 5.2 Presence (dot) of earthworm species at each of the nine European pedoclimatic regions. atl_cent = Atlantic Central; atl_north = Atlantic North; boreal = Boreal; cont = Continental; lusit = Lusitanian; med_north = Mediterranean North; med_south = Mediterranean South; nemoral = Nemoral; pann = Pannonian.

farmers tend to switch to reduced tillage systems which mitigate mechanical impacts on earthworms. The differences between the two farming systems may also be sometimes less clearly defined: organic fertilizers are used in both systems as are rotations with leys and crop diversification, crop residues left or removed from the field surface, etc.. Usage of pesticides in conventional farming may also often remain in a level which is not harmful for earthworms. Using the field metadata, refined analyses of the data needs to account for all the relevant local variation in environment and field management.

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ANNEXES-tables

TABLE A1.1

SOURCE	F	R2	<i>P</i>
Region	70.5699	0.73391	0.001
Management	2.4782	0.00322	0.042
Region & Management	4.0262	0.04187	0.001
Residuals		0.22100	

Table A1.1. Results of PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of region, management (organic or conventional management) and the interaction between them on the bacterial OTU composition. Differences are considered significant if $p \leq 0.05$.

TABLE A1.2

SOURCE	F	R2	<i>P</i>
Region	44.0606	0.65229	0.001
Management	1.9465	0.00360	0.078
Region & Management	1.9932	0.02951	0.003
Residuals		0.31460	

Table A1.2. Results of PERMANOVA analysis to test the effect of region, management (organic or conventional management) and the interaction between them on the Archaeal OTU composition. Differences are considered significant if $p \leq 0.05$.

TABLE A2.1

REGION	SIMPER (%)	P	PHYLUM/ORDER	FAMILY	GENUS	GUILD
Conv vs. org						
Pann	1.3 %	0.02	A: Thelebolales	<i>Pseudeurotiaceae</i>	<i>Pseudogymnoascus</i>	sap
	1.2 %	0.05	B: Tremellales	<i>Trimorphomycetaceae</i>	<i>Saitozyma</i>	unid
Lusit	11.2 %	0.003	A: Pezizales	<i>Pyronemataceae</i>	<i>Pseudaleuria</i>	sap
	1.9 %	0.005	A: Sordariales	<i>Chaetomiaceae</i>	<i>Botryotrichum</i>	sap
	6.0 %	0.003	A: Sordariales	<i>Chaetomiaceae</i>	<i>Humicola</i>	sap
	1.6 %	0.02	A: Pleosporales	<i>Leptosphaeriaceae</i>	<i>Plenodomus</i>	sap
	3.0 %	0.003	B: Trichosporonales	<i>Trichosporonaceae</i>	<i>Apiotrichum</i>	sap
	1.4 %	0.03	B: Tremellales	<i>Bulleribasidiaceae</i>	<i>Vishniacozyma</i>	unid
	1.4 %	0.04	M: Mortierellales	<i>Mortierellaceae</i>	<i>Mortierella</i>	sap-sym
Nemoral	1.0 %	0.005	A: Capnodiales	<i>Cladosporiaceae</i>	<i>Cladosporium</i>	unid
	1.1 %	0.02	A: Sordariales	<i>Lasiosphaeriaceae</i>	unidentified	sap
	1.1 %	0.005	A: Hypocreales	<i>Nectriaceae</i>	<i>Dactylonectria</i>	sap-pat-sym
	2.2 %	0.05	M: Mortierellales	<i>Mortierellaceae</i>	<i>Mortierella</i>	sap-sym
Org vs. conv						
Med_South	2.0 %	0.04	A: Capnodiales	<i>Cladosporiaceae</i>	<i>Cladosporium</i>	unid
	6.3 %	0.001	A: Capnodiales	<i>Mycosphaerellaceae</i>	<i>Mycosphaerella</i>	pat
	1.6 %	0.02	A: Eurotiales	<i>Aspergillaceae</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>	unid
	1.5 %	0.008	A: Eurotiales	<i>Aspergillaceae</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>	unid
	2.2 %	0.001	A: Hypocreales	<i>Nectriaceae</i>	unidentified	sap-pat-sym
	2.8 %	0.002	A: Hypocreales	<i>Stachybotryaceae</i>	<i>Stachybotrys</i>	unid
	1.6 %	0.03	A: Pleosporales	<i>Pleosporaceae</i>	<i>Alternaria</i>	sap-pat-sym
	2.4 %	0.001	A: Pleosporales	<i>Pleosporaceae</i>	<i>Alternaria</i>	sap-pat-sym

	2.4 %	0.001	A: Pleosporales	<i>Sporormiaceae</i>	<i>Preussia</i>	sap
	1.5 %	0.002	A: Pleosporales	<i>Sporormiaceae</i>	<i>Preussia</i>	sap
	1.4 %	0.004	A: unidentified	unidentified	unidentified	unid
	1.3 %	0.01	A: Filobasidiales	<i>Filobasidiaceae</i>	<i>Filobasidium</i>	sap
	1.8 %	0.03	A: Filobasidiales	<i>Piskurozymaceae</i>	<i>Solicoccozyma</i>	unid
	1.6 %	0.009	A: Mortierellales	<i>Mortierellaceae</i>	<i>Mortierella</i>	sap-sym
	2.3 %	0.001	unidentified Fungi	unidentified Fungi	unidentified Fungi	unid
	10.1 %	0.03	unidentified Fungi	unidentified Fungi	unidentified Fungi	unid

Table A2.3 Results of the SIMPER analysis with taxonomic and functional profiles of the OTUs that contributed more than 1% to beta-diversity between organic and conventional management systems (e.g. OTUs which are the most abundant and/or most variable). $p < 0.05$. Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic, Pat = pathotroph, Sap = saprotroph, Sym = symbiotroph, unid = unidentified.

TABLE A4.1

CODE	#	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
ACC1A	6385	308	4	68	0	0	0	0	1
ACC2A	7000	616	16	8	0	0	0	264	8
ACC3A	4508	248	0	24	0	0	0	0	0
ACC4A	8713	616	0	0	24	0	1	0	0
ACC5A	3976	88	8	104	8	0	0	0	0
ACC6A	4976	172	4	0	0	0	4	8	8
ACC6B	4224	56	0	0	8	0	8	0	0
ACC7A	5892	400	0	0	32	0	8	0	220
ACC8A	6608	144	0	0	56	0	0	0	32
ACC8B	13882	2272	2	0	0	0	0	0	488
ACC9A	5984	400	208	0	0	0	0	0	8
ACC10A	3728	776	0	0	0	0	0	24	16
ACC11A	1296	32	0	16	0	0	0	0	4
ACO1A	3800	144	8	0	0	0	0	0	16
ACO1B	2576	88	0	0	0	0	0	8	0
ACO1C	4769	192	48	24	0	1	0	56	64
ACO2A	6912	1144	104	0	0	0	0	48	168
ACO3A	1452	304	0	0	16	0	0	0	0
ACO4A	2702	70	0	0	10	2	0	90	180
ACO4B	7368	200	352	16	32	24	0	120	32
ACO4C	8905	304	320	0	12	1	0	1500	0
ACO5A	6142	1660	0	10	30	2	0	0	270
ACO5B	7802	950	690	0	20	2	0	90	40
ACO6A	5896	1024	0	16	8	0	16	0	16
ACO6B	924	16	4	0	0	0	0	4	4
ANC1A	5460	180	24	0	28	0	0	392	0
ANC1B	6000	125	0	0	55	0	0	1040	0
ANC2A	5036	104	8	0	72	0	0	16	0
ANC2B	5200	104	336	8	28	0	4	0	0
ANC3A	2268	48	64	0	20	0	8	0	0
ANC3B	3716	340	68	0	12	0	0	16	4
ANC4A	3520	20	740	0	4	0	0	8	52
ANC4B	5336	80	168	0	0	4	4	24	20
ANC5A	3955	130	325	0	0	0	0	10	0
ANC5B	2976	25	900	0	1	0	0	50	15

ANO1A	3828	232	0	0	0	0	0	4	0
ANO1B	3036	44	0	0	0	0	0	4	0
ANO2A	5696	104	0	0	4	0	0	116	36
ANO2B	7263	192	0	0	12	3	12	200	56
ANO3A	3504	44	88	4	0	0	4	24	56
ANO3B	2992	40	24	4	0	0	12	0	28
ANO4A	5252	264	0	0	64	0	0	12	4
ANO4B	3030	145	45	0	0	0	0	0	25
ANO5A	3640	28	20	0	0	0	0	48	108
ANO5B	3180	48	256	0	0	0	0	8	4
BORC1A	1449	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	1
BORC1B	1537	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BORC2A	912	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BORC2B	2017	1	0	0	0	0	0	24	8
BORC3A	4867	272	0	0	0	0	3	48	0
BORC3B	2203	368	0	0	0	0	1	8	2
BORC4A	2883	104	0	0	0	0	3	48	0
BORC4B	1856	64	0	0	0	0	0	24	40
BORC5A	452	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	10
BORC5B	1390	60	0	0	0	0	0	140	0
BORO1A	2112	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	88
BORO1B	2664	16	0	0	0	0	0	8	24
BORO2A	4104	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
BORO2B	3509	3	0	0	0	0	2	16	56
BORO3A	3745	360	0	0	1	0	0	24	0
BORO3B	3100	296	0	0	0	4	0	72	0
BORO4A	6824	88	0	0	0	0	8	40	344
BORO4B	3200	600	0	8	0	0	0	120	0
BORO5A	792	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16
BORO5B	4537	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
CONC1A	7027	672	1	24	0	0	2	124	0
CONC1B	9426	1196	0	8	0	0	6	156	0
CONC1C	8632	624	0	12	0	0	4	116	0
CONC2A	6124	256	0	24	0	0	4	0	0
CONC2B	13500	640	1	0	0	1	2	0	0
CONC2C	7730	424	0	16	0	0	2	0	0
CONC3A	11012	400	0	0	0	0	4	8	0
CONC3B	12194	176	0	16	0	2	0	152	0
CONC3C	9034	1496	0	8	0	0	2	216	0
CONC4A	3432	312	0	24	0	0	0	24	0
CONO1A	5001	352	0	0	0	0	1	16	0

CONO1B	7352	208	0	0	0	0	0	40	0
CONO1C	8818	2464	0	0	0	0	2	184	0
CONO2A	12236	536	0	0	0	0	4	64	0
CONO2B	20620	820	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CONO2C	8772	590	0	2	0	0	0	250	0
CONO3A	3552	216	0	0	0	0	0	8	0
CONO4A	8608	272	0	0	0	0	0	184	0
CONO4B	7215	368	0	2	1	0	4	80	0
CONO4C	8962	712	0	0	0	2	0	96	0
LUSC1A	1129	64	0	152	0	0	1	16	0
LUSC1B	2016	232	648	184	0	0	0	0	0
LUSC2A	5400	2184	0	24	0	0	0	0	0
LUSC2B	1889	688	0	16	0	0	1	0	0
LUSC3A	2512	192	688	272	0	0	0	0	0
LUSC3B	2818	320	0	136	32	0	2	24	0
LUSC4A	2384	752	88	16	0	0	0	0	0
LUSC4B	2248	368	344	160	0	0	0	0	8
LUSC5A	19042	260	18140	0	0	0	2	0	0
LUSC5B	5220	124	0	8	0	0	16	4	0
LUSO1A	1603	4	28	0	0	0	3	0	0
LUSO1B	3832	256	12	0	0	0	0	0	28
LUSO2A	6133	136	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
LUSO2B	6753	246	0	16	0	0	2	12	1
LUSO3A	2256	96	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
LUSO3B	2000	152	0	12	0	0	0	0	0
LUSO4A	3834	208	4	8	1	0	1	20	0
LUSO4B	5661	248	3628	24	1	0	0	40	0
LUSO4C	3145	424	600	12	0	0	0	40	0
LUSO5A	4524	140	68	16	4	8	0	8	104
LUSO5B	4305	480	964	0	1	2	2	0	52
LUSO6A	3332	1148	0	204	0	0	0	0	0
LUSO6B	4572	2024	4	436	0	0	0	0	0
MNC1A	1260	340	0	0	0	1	3	320	0
MNC1B	1406	696	0	0	0	0	2	20	0
MNC2A	1459	84	2	0	0	2	1	2	0
MNC2B	1424	96	56	16	0	0	0	140	0
MNC3A	2416	260	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MNC3B	1916	176	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MNC4A	4112	384	0	80	0	12	0	60	0
MNC4B	5427	260	285	70	0	2	0	25	0
MNC5A	4185	210	0	75	0	0	25	0	0

MNC5B	2108	28	0	4	0	0	12	0	0
MNO1A	1766	52	0	108	0	2	0	76	0
MNO1B	1561	48	0	8	0	0	1	32	0
MNO2A	3546	65	0	0	0	1	0	35	0
MNO2B	3248	24	0	0	0	0	0	92	0
MNO3A	6594	123	0	36	0	7	0	220	0
MNO3B	5104	1024	0	0	0	0	0	140	0
MNO4A	1857	152	0	0	0	1	0	36	0
MNO4B	2996	488	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MNO5A	4936	748	144	0	0	0	0	148	0
MNO5B	2854	132	30	0	0	0	0	40	0
MSC1A	2512	928	0	0	0	0	0	48	0
MSC1B	1756	968	20	20	0	0	0	120	0
MSC2A	1664	468	704	4	0	0	0	80	0
MSC2B	1324	236	20	0	0	0	0	620	0
MSC3A	1324	784	8	8	0	0	0	48	0
MSC3B	628	120	0	0	0	0	4	120	0
MSC4A	1212	100	0	0	0	0	0	440	0
MSC4B	558	28	0	0	0	0	2	48	0
MSC5A	1960	1104	0	0	0	0	28	32	0
MSC5B	3626	840	0	0	0	0	2	44	0
MSO1A	2817	0	1500	0	0	3	2	116	0
MSO1B	4520	20	28	8	0	0	4	24	0
MSO2A	2084	24	44	28	0	0	0	56	0
MSO2B	828	120	4	16	0	0	0	0	0
MSO3A	688	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MSO3B	1932	3	0	2	0	0	0	12	0
MSO4A	1717	45	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
MSO4B	1880	64	0	24	0	0	0	76	0
MSO5A	1568	252	28	12	0	0	4	24	0
MSO5B	1250	90	0	0	0	0	0	85	0
NEMC1A	4989	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	168
NEMC1B	3368	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	96
NEMC2A	5664	256	0	0	0	0	0	120	0
NEMC2B	4824	576	0	0	0	0	0	48	16
NEMC3A	8536	40	0	80	0	0	0	192	128
NEMC3B	7632	104	0	0	0	0	0	72	40
NEMC4A	5132	80	0	0	0	0	4	8	104
NEMC4B	7851	352	0	0	1	1	1	0	24
NEMC5A	5827	2160	0	64	0	3	0	32	80
NEMC5B	7868	4192	0	24	0	0	4	144	16

NEMO1A	7696	276	0	24	0	0	0	44	16
NEMO1B	6132	1660	0	12	0	0	0	12	112
NEMO2A	5540	24	0	0	0	0	8	8	236
NEMO2B	6930	224	0	0	0	2	4	12	268
NEMO3A	5136	260	8	0	0	0	4	12	340
NEMO3B	4842	48	4	16	0	2	8	52	280
NEMO4A	9256	304	0	8	0	0	0	144	256
NEMO4B	6152	728	0	8	0	0	0	48	200
NEMO5A	6522	264	2	0	0	0	0	32	192
NEMO5B	6024	312	2	24	0	0	2	0	52
PANC1A	885	130	1	20	0	0	0	0	2
PANC1B	3123	180	0	72	0	0	1	0	2
PANC2A	2441	228	0	80	0	1	0	0	0
PANC2B	2851	288	0	52	0	1	0	2	0
PANC3A	4955	3004	0	16	0	0	3	0	0
PANC3B	3164	1088	0	36	0	0	0	0	0
PANC4A	2025	929	0	4	0	0	0	4	0
PANC4B	3060	1040	0	88	0	0	0	148	0
PANC5A	2386	360	0	20	0	0	2	140	0
PANC5B	2141	608	0	20	0	0	1	40	0
PANO1A	8749	4552	0	1	0	0	4	4	0
PANO1B	4557	1708	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
PANO2A	3034	632	0	24	0	0	4	44	2
PANO2B	4815	108	0	8	0	1	12	44	2
PANO3A	13140	3280	0	76	0	0	28	0	0
PANO3B	8349	1468	0	24	0	0	9	16	0
PANO4A	3268	400	0	8	0	0	12	0	0
PANO4B	2028	36	0	0	0	0	12	4	0
PANO5A	2844	25	0	0	0	0	25	4	0
PANO5B	5080	156	0	0	0	0	16	68	0

Table A4.4 Absolute number of nematode individuals (#) and of certain economically important plant-parasitic nematode genera (A-H). A: *Pratylenchus* spp., B: *Meloidogyne* spp., C: *Globodera* and *Heterodera* spp., D: Trichodoridae, E: *Xiphinema* and *Longidorus* spp., F: *Ditylenchus* spp., G: *Paratylenchus* spp., H: *Rotylenchus* spp.

ANNEXES-figures

Figure A1.1. Mean relative abundance (%) of the most abundant Archaeal phyla for each pedoclimatic region; Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian.

Figure A1.2. Average number of observed bacterial OTUs between management practise in the different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region and includes both management practices.

Significant differences in values were obtained with t-test (p -values: **** <0.0001, *** <0.001, ** <0.01, * <0.05). Significant differences in values were obtained with t-test (p -values: **** <0.0001, *** <0.001, ** <0.01, * <0.05). Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Figure A1.3. Average Shannon indices of the bacterial OTUs between management practice in the different regions. Each panel corresponds to a specific pedoclimatic region and includes both agricultural management systems. Significant differences in values were obtained with t-test (p -values: **** <0.0001, *** <0.001, ** <0.01, * <0.05). Alt_cent = Atlantic Central, Alt_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Figure A1.4. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the bacterial OTU composition of the different pedoclimatic regions. The pedoclimatic regions are indicated by colour, the agricultural management system by shape. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Figure A1.5. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the Archaeal OTU composition of the different pedoclimatic regions. The pedoclimatic regions are indicated by colour, the agricultural management system by shape. Atl_cent = Atlantic Central, Atl_north = Atlantic North, Boreal = Boreal, Cont = Continental, Lusit = Lusitanian, Med_north = Mediterranean North, Med_south = Mediterranean South, Nemoral = Nemoral, Pann = Pannonian, conv = conventional and org = organic.

Figure A1.6. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic agricultural management system at the Atlantic Central region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A1.7. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic agricultural management system at the Atlantic North region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A1.8. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming systems at the Boreal region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A1.9. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Continental region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A1.10. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Lusitanian region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log

fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A.1.11. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Mediterranean North region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A1.12. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Mediterranean South region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A1.13. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Nemoral region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log

fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A1.14. Bacterial OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Pannonian region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A2.1a. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Atlantic Central region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each

point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure 2.1b. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Atlantic North region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure 2.1c. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Boreal region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A2.1d. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Continental region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A2.1e. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Lusitanian region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A2.1f. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Mediterranean North region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A2.1g. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Mediterranean South region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A2.1h. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Nemoral region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.

Figure A2.1i. Fungal OTUs which were differential abundant between conventional and organic farming system at the Pannonian region as determined by differential abundance analysis (ANCOMBC). Each point of the plot represent a specific OTU significantly impacted by agricultural management system. OTUs with a log fold change above zero are significantly associated with organic farming system and those with values below zero are significantly associated with conventional farming system. The genera of the differential abundant OTUs are indicated by the names on the x-axis and the colour of the points indicates which phylum the OTUs belongs to.